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REPORT ON ONE CONSUMER SURVEY AND PRODUCT TESTING AND BRIEF

D8.15

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Report on one consumer survey and product testing and brief

1. Scope of Deliverable 8.15

Deliverable 8.15, carried out in the context of WP8 on communication, dissemination and exploitation, summarizes the outcome of three consumers surveys aimed at understanding and analysing how consumers react to FuturEnzyme innovations and in particular if they are willing to buy sustainable enzyme-based products. The surveys, engaging a total of around 2500 consumers across Europe, are based on the Choice Experiment approach which was adopted for each of the three products targeted by the project: a standard liquid detergent in a 1.5 L format; a T-shirt made of polyester; a face cream with hyaluronic acid in a 30 mL format.

Although some of the enzymes developed in the project proved to be effective for certain applications, efficient, sustainable, and high-quality manufacturing—as well as assessments of safety, efficacy, and scalability—and subsequent regulatory approval cannot be completed within the typical timeframes of funded projects. Therefore, the testing activity initially foreseen for this deliverable was replaced by the three consumer surveys mentioned above, along with extensive communication and dissemination activities targeting consumers. These were carried out in collaboration with Euroconsumers and Altroconsumo, two relevant consumer associations in Europe and Italy, respectively. A summary of these activities is provided in **Deliverable D8.17**.

2. Executive Summary

Deliverable D8.15 presents the results of a comprehensive consumer preference analysis conducted under the FuturEnzyme project, targeting three high-impact consumer products: laundry detergents, polyester-based textiles, and hyaluronic acid-based cosmetics. The primary aim of this study was to evaluate how European consumers respond to sustainability-related innovations in these product categories, particularly focusing on their willingness to pay (WTP) for specific environmental attributes.

The study employed a Choice Experiment (CE) methodology based on a structured and validated workflow developed by the project partners. Three separate surveys—one for each product category—were developed using standardized experimental designs and disseminated across multiple European countries. The detergent survey engaged 304 participants through open-access distribution, while the textile and cosmetic surveys gathered 1031 and 1019 responses respectively through structured and demographically balanced consumer panels. Each product was described by a combination of conventional and sustainability-related attributes, covering areas such as packaging, ingredient origin, energy or water use, emissions, microplastic release, and recycled content. Respondents evaluated trade-offs between these attributes through choice sets, enabling estimation of their WTP for each feature.

Across the three product types, the results consistently showed a strong valuation of sustainability-related improvements. For detergents, attributes such as reduced plastic use and renewable surfactants received higher WTP than even product performance features like stain removal. For textiles, a 50% recycled fibre content and reductions in energy and microplastic emissions were most valued. In cosmetics, refillable packaging and carbon-neutral production were among the top-valued attributes, along with biodegradable and bio-based ingredients. Sociodemographic segmentation revealed differentiated patterns of preference, including gender-based and age-related variations, although these varied across product categories. Importantly, the study found differences between stated and revealed preferences. Survey responses often emphasized product effectiveness and price, while choice behaviors in the CE highlighted a stronger emphasis on sustainability. This divergence underscores the complexity of consumer decision-making and the value of using CE to capture latent drivers of choice.

The results presented in this document, thereby, provide actionable insights into how sustainability features influence consumer decision-making in the detergent, textile, and cosmetic sectors, with potential implications for product design, marketing strategies, and R&D planning.

3. Introduction

3.1 The impact of consumer products on the environment: the detergent, cosmetic and textile case studies

In recent years, the environmental impact of our production and consumption systems has become increasingly visible. The combined effect of fossil fuel use, overexploitation of natural resources, and inefficient industrial processes is accelerating climate change and putting severe pressure on ecosystems. Among the main contributors to this situation are consumer products, which affect the environment throughout their life cycle—from resource extraction to production, use, and disposal (Ivanova et al., 2016).

Consumer goods, especially those used daily such as detergents, textiles, and cosmetics, are responsible for a large share of global environmental impact. It is estimated that these products account for around 60% of global greenhouse gas emissions and up to 80% of global resource use, including land, water, and raw materials (Ivanova et al., 2016). Their production often requires high energy inputs, large volumes of water, and the use of synthetic chemicals, many of which persist in the environment or require complex treatments at the end of the product's life (Tore et al., 2013).

In the chemical industry, many processes used to produce these goods are still based on non-selective reactions and harsh operating conditions. This leads to low yields, high energy costs, and the generation of significant amounts of waste. Reactions at high temperatures or extreme pH levels require additional steps that consume even more resources and increase the volume of effluents. At the end of the product's life, improper disposal or poor degradability of chemical components further increases the environmental burden (Tore et al., 2016).

A typical household in Europe uses around 16–20 kg of laundry detergent and 9,000 liters of water annually for washing clothes. These detergents contain surfactants and additives that are often not fully removed by wastewater treatment plants and contribute to aquatic pollution (Molina-Espeja et al., 2023). Laundry detergents significantly affect the environment due to their chemical ingredients, production methods, and disposal practices. These impacts raise concerns related to water pollution, ecosystem degradation, and potential human health risks (De Moura et al., 2024; Gosteiijn et al., 2015). According to Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) studies, the usage phase, particularly the energy demands of washing machines and consumer behavior, represents around 60% of the total carbon emissions linked to these products. Additionally, the formulation of the detergents contributes roughly 20% to their environmental footprint (Cortez et al., 2024). Traditional detergents often include phosphates, synthetic surfactants, and other non-biodegradable substances, which can intensify eutrophication, threaten biodiversity, and introduce pollutants into aquatic environments and food systems. The widespread use of single-use plastic packaging further compounds the issue of solid waste accumulation (Gupta & Sekhri, 2014; Mousavi & Khodadoost, 2019).

The fashion and textile industries are estimated to be responsible for 8–10% of global CO₂ emissions, approximately 20% of industrial water pollution, and over 92 million tonnes of textile waste each year (Celine & Kaufman, 2024). Producing 30 kg of clothing per year, about the average for a European consumer, generates 124 kg of CO₂, uses 150 liters of water, and consumes energy comparable to the annual usage of a small household (Molina-Espeja et al., 2023). Textile products pose a substantial environmental challenge due to their resource-intensive production, chemical usage, and end-of-life disposal practices. The increasing demand driven by fast fashion has amplified problems related to water consumption, land use, and greenhouse gas emissions. Life cycle assessments show that textile production is one of the largest contributors to global water pollution—accounting for roughly 20% of clean water contamination, primarily

from dyeing and finishing processes. Synthetic garments further intensify the environmental burden through the release of microplastics during washing, with an estimated 700,000 microfibrils shed per load of polyester clothing. These nano- and microplastics accumulate in oceans (at concentrations of between 0.04 and 1.17 µg/L; Okoffo and Thomas, 2024), posing threats to marine ecosystems and potentially entering the food system. Moreover, textile waste management remains problematic. Less than 1% of used clothing is recycled into new textiles, with the vast majority either landfilled or incinerated¹.

The cosmetic industry, a fast-growing global sector, faces mounting pressure to mitigate its environmental footprint. The production of cosmetics, even in small volumes (~1 kg per household per year), releases chemical substances comparable to the emissions of a car driving 6 km (Molina-Espeja et al., 2023). From sourcing raw materials to post-consumer waste, every phase of a product's life cycle contributes to environmental degradation. Manufacturing processes consume significant amounts of energy and water, while also generating emissions and chemical waste. Many formulations still rely on synthetic ingredients, some of which are associated with environmental toxicity and poor biodegradability. Moreover, packaging, particularly single-use plastics, remains a critical environmental concern, with low recycling rates and high pollution risks (Mondello et al., 2024; Wirtu, 2024).

In a context where global population continues to grow and natural resources are increasingly limited, the challenge is to design new production methods that reduce environmental impact while meeting consumer needs. One of the most promising solutions is offered by industrial biotechnology, and in particular by the use of enzymes.

3.2 Green Trends in Consumer Products

Over the past years, environmental concerns, such as climate change, resource depletion, and plastic pollution, have significantly influenced consumer awareness and behaviour. People are increasingly recognizing the role that everyday products play in contributing to global environmental problems and are showing greater interest in alternatives that promise lower ecological impact. This growing environmental awareness is now reflected in consumer preferences, industry strategies, and market dynamics.

According to recent surveys, a substantial proportion of European citizens consider climate change the most pressing global challenge. In particular, 49% of Europeans consider climate change to be the most prominent global challenge² and 64% are already making environmentally conscious choices in their daily lives³. The shift toward sustainable consumption is not only seen in attitudes but also in purchasing decisions: many consumers actively seek out eco-labeled, biodegradable, or ethically sourced products, especially in categories like food, clothing, cosmetics, and home care (Saija et al., 2023).

Today, 50% of consumers rank sustainability among the top five value factors when making a purchase, and on average, more than a third (34%) of the population is willing to pay a premium for sustainable products or services—typically exceeding 25%. The willingness to pay a higher price is greatest in consumer goods (38%) and lowest in the energy/utilities sector (31%). This indicates that, as consumers increasingly prioritize the green factor in their purchasing behavior, companies will face significant pressure to demonstrate their sustainability credentials and continue to make sustainability a core part of their value proposition—while also maintaining affordable prices⁴.

¹ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20201208STO93327/the-impact-of-textile-production-and-waste-on-the-environment-infographics>

² https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_447

³ https://italy.representation.ec.europa.eu/notizie-ed-eventi/notizie/indagine-eurobarometro-gli-europei-considerano-i-cambiamenti-climatici-il_it

⁴ <https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20211014005090/en/Recent->

Subsequent research has focused on understanding consumer purchasing behavior and perceptions in specific areas of interest, in order to obtain more accurate data to support businesses in shaping their development strategies. It is indeed essential to determine whether the green trend among consumers is consistent across most consumer products or if certain goods attract more attention and sensitivity than others.

In the three sectors targeted by FuturEnzyme, consumer demand for sustainability is particularly relevant. The fashion sector is increasingly attentive to the type of raw materials used in clothing production and to the environmental impact of manufacturing processes. In Italy, nearly half of respondents consider brands' sustainability practices to be important, and specifically, 39% of customers are influenced by the environmental impact of production and the types of packaging used. Additionally, 79% of respondents report checking the origin of raw materials in the products they purchase, and about half are highly inclined to buy a product made with a new recyclable raw material (such as plant-based or fruit-derived fibers). This indicates that, even in the fashion sector, alignment with a more circular economy is becoming an increasingly important purchasing driver, pushing companies to promote greener garments made, for example, from recycled materials (e.g., recycled cotton, polyester, viscose)⁵.

The demand for products containing natural ingredients and geared toward environmental sustainability is also a steadily growing trend in the cosmetics industry. This has led companies in the sector to focus on producing sustainable cosmetics that both meet new consumer demands and reduce the environmental impact of one of the largest industries. A recent study shows that the value of cosmetics featuring organic or naturally derived ingredients (natural/organic cosmetics) and those that are environmentally, socially, and economically sustainable throughout their life cycle (sustainable/green cosmetics) amounts to €925 million. Consumers are particularly attentive to ingredient origin, product content, and the environmental impact from production to end-of-life. Specifically, 75% of women aged 18 to 34 stated that purchasing sustainable cosmetics is very important to them, and more than two out of three read ingredient labels on beauty products before buying them⁶.

Sustainability is also an important factor in purchasing decisions in the detergent sector. In particular, 72% of European consumers actively consider the sustainability aspects when making purchasing decisions, reflecting a growing preference for features such as biodegradable ingredients, a reduction in chemical toxicity, and sustainable packaging^{7 8 9}.

In conclusion, these data clearly show that consumer trends are increasingly shifting toward a green market. Understanding how consumers perceive and evaluate sustainability is essential for guiding the development of innovative and environmentally responsible products. This knowledge plays a decisive role in determining which product categories should be prioritized, which sustainability features are most valued, and where to concentrate research and development efforts. Without this understanding, there is a significant risk of allocating resources toward solutions that, although effective from a technical or environmental standpoint, may fail to generate interest or acceptance in the market.

What makes this understanding even more critical is the fact that sustainability is not perceived as a single concept, but rather as a set of diverse and specific attributes, each with different levels of importance to different consumer segments. Features such as packaging reduction, biodegradability, low energy and water

⁵ <https://news.sap.com/italy/2021/06/nuova-ricerca-sap-gli-italiani-mostrano-sempre-piu-interesse-a-conoscere-le-pratiche-di-sostenibilita-dei-brand/>

⁶ https://adu.unibo.it/osservatoriopack/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Consumatori-Cosmetica-Packaging_Unibo-Quantis-Cosmetica-2.pdf

⁷ <https://www.statista.com/study/55498/home-and-laundry-care-market-data-and-analysis/>

⁸ <https://www.marketresearchfuture.com/reports/organic-laundry-detergent-market-24448>

⁹ <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2791/0171>

use, reduced carbon footprint, or chemical safety can all be perceived differently depending on personal values, habits, and demographic factors (Saija et al., 2023). An in-depth analysis of consumer perspectives is therefore required to capture these nuances and identify which specific sustainability attributes actually influence purchasing decisions and justify a willingness to pay.

This level of detail is not only relevant for product development, but also for market positioning and business strategy. The heterogeneity of consumer responses confirms the need for classification of goods based on their sustainability features, which can be leveraged to tailor communication strategies, optimize product portfolios, and support evidence-based marketing. In other words, knowing not just that consumers care about sustainability, but what kind of sustainability they care about enables more targeted, efficient, and successful innovation.

4. Methodology

4.1 The Choice Experiment methodology

The Choice Experiment (CE) is a stated preference method widely used in marketing, economics, and behavioral research to identify which product or service attributes influence individual purchasing preferences. Unlike methods that isolate a single variable, CE allows for the evaluation of complex goods and services as a whole, reflecting more accurately how real-life decisions are made (Aalbers et al., 2015).

The method is based on an experimental survey design, composed of multiple scenarios, known as *choice sets*. In each set, respondents are presented with several product alternatives, each defined by a combination of product features, referred to as *attributes*, which are expressed at varying degrees (*levels*). In the context of Choice Experiments, attributes represent the key characteristics or features of the good or service under evaluation. Each attribute is designed to capture a specific dimension of consumer preference or product quality. The levels, in turn, indicate the range of possible values or intensities that each attribute can assume, reflecting the options that respondents may weigh during their decision-making process (Snowball JD, 2008). Within each scenario, respondents are asked to select their preferred alternative from those provided. The combinations of attribute levels across alternatives are systematically constructed according to statistical design principles, enabling researchers to understand the value that individuals assign to each specific product characteristic (Aoki & Akai, 2022).

The theoretical foundation of the CE is the Random Utility Theory (RUT). This theory assumes that when faced with a set of alternatives, individuals choose the option that maximizes their utility. It also suggests that a product or service can be characterized by its individual components, and that a respondent's overall utility—or preference—for the product or service is determined by the value they derive from each of these components.

The results are therefore interpreted as utility coefficients, which in turn enable the quantification of additional metrics such as choice probability, market share, elasticity, and willingness to pay (WTP)—that is, the potential premium price for a specific good or service—by estimating its value based on its characteristics and anticipated demand (Mariel et al., 2021; Snowball JD, 2008).

In addition to the main experimental design, CE surveys are often supplemented with demographic and socioeconomic data, including age, gender, income level, education, lifestyle, purchasing habits, attitudes, and knowledge of the product or topic. This allows for segmentation of preferences and WTP, offering a more comprehensive understanding of the diversity in consumer behavior (Snowball JD, 2008; Willis KG, 2014).

Despite its strengths, the CE method has inherent limitations. One of the most frequently cited is the **hypothetical bias**, which refers to discrepancies between what individuals say they would do in a hypothetical situation and what they would actually do in real life. This often results in an overestimation or underestimation of WTP, affecting the accuracy and reliability of results (Aoki & Akai, 2022; Buckell et al.,

2020). Several factors contribute to this bias, such as the non-binding nature of survey responses, the disconnect between survey conditions and real purchasing contexts (e.g., completing a survey online versus shopping in a store), or social desirability bias, where respondents provide answers, they believe are more acceptable or desirable to others (Buckell et al., 2020; Menapace & Raffaelli, 2020).

A second common limitation is **sample bias**, which arises when the sample is not representative of the broader population. This could stem from small sample sizes, demographic imbalances (e.g., non-homogeneous age or gender distribution), or inconsistencies between the pilot and final survey samples (Snowball JD, 2008; Willis KG, 2014). To enhance the robustness and market relevance of CE results, researchers must take these potential sources of bias into account during both the design and analysis phases.

An important preliminary consideration when implementing CE methodology is the **definition of the "consumer" and "buyer"**. According to EU consumer protection law, specifically Directive 2011/83/EU and its amendment 2019/2161/EU, a consumer is defined as "any natural person who, in contracts covered by the directive, is acting for purposes which are outside his trade, business, craft or profession". While this legal definition is the most commonly applied in regulatory contexts, it does not fully align with definitions used in marketing and social sciences, which often distinguish between the buyer (or customer)—the individual who purchases a good or service—and the consumer—the one who actually uses it (Margus Kingisepp AV, 2011). In marketing and sociological terms, buyers are those who make the transaction, while consumers are those who benefit from the use of the product or service¹⁰. These two roles may or may not overlap. In the context of a choice experiment, the distinction is relevant, as the goal is to simulate a realistic purchase scenario. Therefore, the term "consumer" generally refers to an individual who both purchases and uses the product, aligning with both legal and behavioral interpretations depending on the perspective adopted.

4.2 The workflow design

As part of a broader effort to improve the consistency and robustness of Choice Experiment (CE) studies applied to sustainable consumer goods, a structured workflow was developed and published by the research team in the article "*A Choice Experiment Model for Sustainable Consumer Goods: A Systematic Literature Review and Workflow Design*" (Saija et al., 2023).

The publication is based on a systematic literature review of 186 CE studies published between 2012 and 2022, selected through the PRISMA methodology. The aim was to identify recurring limitations and inconsistencies in CE design applied to consumer products with sustainability attributes. The review analysed various methodological elements, including product selection, definition of attributes and levels, choice set structure, sample design, and bias control strategies.

From this meta-analysis, it was found that many studies lacked clarity in the definition of sustainability, often relying on vague or generalized terms such as "eco-friendly" or "green" without specifying the actual feature being evaluated (e.g., biodegradability, carbon footprint, packaging recyclability). Inconsistencies were also found in the number of attributes used (ranging from two to ten) and the use of attributes that were either too technical or not interpretable by the general public.

As a response, the study proposes a **six-phase workflow** to guide the design of CE studies (**Figure 1** from Saija et al., 2023).

¹⁰ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/customer> & <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/consumer?q=consumers>

Figure 1. Choice experiment workflow developed by Saija et al, 2023.

The main elements of the workflow and the corresponding findings from the literature analysis are as follows:

1. **Select a neutral and familiar target product.** Choosing a product that is not strongly associated with a specific demographic (e.g., gender, age, or income group) increases generalizability and avoids sampling bias. Studies that used neutral products (e.g., unisex clothing or basic hygiene items) reported greater response consistency and higher engagement, while niche products often led to lower comprehension or skewed data.
2. **Define 3–5 clear and interpretable attributes with 10–15 levels total.** Using a limited number of well-defined, realistic attributes reduces respondent fatigue and improves result clarity. The review found that studies falling within this range showed higher internal validity and fewer cases of “lack of attributes/levels” among reported limitations. Overly complex designs with more than six attributes often led to cognitive overload and lower data quality.
3. **Construct 8–9 choice sets per respondent, each with three alternatives including a no-choice option.** This configuration was identified as the optimal balance between design efficiency and cognitive manageability. Studies using 8–9 sets with a “none of the above” option achieved higher simulation realism and reduced forced-choice bias, helping capture more accurate consumer trade-offs.
4. **Recruit 100–600 respondents with a demographically balanced sample.** The analysis showed that sample bias was the second most common limitation in CE studies. Surveys with balanced distributions by age, gender, education, and geography generated more stable WTP estimates and were better suited for segmentation analyses. Studies with non-representative samples often failed to produce generalizable results.

5. **Select the most appropriate model for analysis based on sample and study goals.** While the Conditional Logit Model (CLM) remains common, the review highlighted a growing preference for Mixed Logit Models (MLM), especially when accounting for preference heterogeneity. Studies using more advanced models reported more nuanced insights into attribute-level trade-offs, especially when supported by sociodemographic segmentation.
6. **Integrate strategies to minimize bias and improve comprehension.** Including visual elements such as labels, explanatory banners, and familiar terminology improved participant understanding and response reliability. Several studies demonstrated that the presence of sustainability labels, even hypothetical, enhanced the perceived value of green attributes and encouraged more reflective decision-making.

For full methodological details and data analysis, refer to: Saija, M.E.; Daniotti, S.; Bosco, D.; Re, I. (2023). *A Choice Experiment Model for Sustainable Consumer Goods, Sustainability*, 15(17), 13183. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151713183>

4.3 The case studies methodology

The design and implementation of the Choice Experiment (CE) in this study were informed and structured following the standardized workflow developed by Saija et al. (2023). This workflow provides a step-by-step framework for designing, testing, and administering choice experiments (CEs) that are both statistically robust and behaviorally realistic.

The methodology was identical for all three consumer product categories investigated in the FuturEnzyme project—laundry detergents, polyester-based textiles, and hyaluronic acid-based cosmetics—with only minor changes and adjustments to reflect the nature of each product. The same structure, logic, and procedure were applied across all survey versions to enable comparability of results and cross-sectoral insights.

4.3.1 Selection of the product types

In the experimental design, the identification of the target product and its key features that consumers prioritize when purchasing laundry detergents, textiles, and cosmetics was informed by a comprehensive literature review, with some of the main findings being summarized in the Introduction section. A detailed analysis of articles, reviews, textbook chapters, and publications from 2015 to 2025, particularly from the last four years (2021–2025), was conducted through databases such as Google Scholar, PubMed, and Elsevier, using targeted keywords to explore aspects like *sustainability*, *purchase choice*, *product formulation*, and *consumer behavior* for each product category.

- **Laundry Detergents**

Findings from Kamwendo and Maharaj (2022) highlighted a pronounced consumer preference for **liquid detergents** over other formats, with a clear inclination towards **smaller packaging sizes**. Based on these insights, the current study focused on a **standard laundry liquid detergent in a 1.5 L format**. This choice was motivated by the product's widespread familiarity and frequent use across diverse population segments, helping to minimize potential bias linked to age, gender, or product familiarity.

- **Textiles**

For the textile product, a **T-shirt made of polyester (PES)** was selected. The decision to use a T-shirt was based on its unisex nature and widespread use, making it a garment that is equally purchased and worn by individuals regardless of gender, age, educational background, or income. This universality helped eliminate potential variability linked to socio-demographic factors. The choice of polyester as the material directly aligns with FuturEnzyme's research focus on enzyme-based innovations for synthetic fabrics.

- **Cosmetics**

In accordance with the project’s objectives, the selected cosmetic product was one based on **hyaluronic acid**. A **30 mL format** was chosen following a market analysis, which identified it as the most used size for facial cosmetic products. No further specification was made regarding the product type (e.g., cream, serum, gel), as this detail was not relevant to the structure of the study nor necessary for the interpretation of consumer preference regarding sustainability features.

However, unlike detergents and textiles, cosmetics cannot be considered a neutral product in terms of consumer familiarity and market exposure. It is widely recognized that cosmetic usage is more prevalent among female consumers, making them more likely to be familiar with hyaluronic acid products than male consumers. This potential knowledge imbalance was carefully considered during both the questionnaire design and the result interpretation phases. Specific response options were introduced to identify participants unfamiliar with the product, ensuring that their data could be appropriately weighted or excluded in the preference analysis to preserve the robustness of the findings.

4.3.2 Selection of attributes and levels

The process of selecting product attributes and corresponding levels was guided by the reference workflow outlined by Saija et al. (2023), which recommends using **3 to 5 attributes with a total of 10–15 levels**. This range is considered optimal to capture the most relevant product features while maintaining cognitive manageability for respondents and minimizing fatigue or decision overload.

A slight exception to this guideline was made for the textile product, where six attributes were included instead of five. This adjustment was necessary to ensure that all fundamental characteristics relevant to the objectives of the FuturEnzyme project could be adequately investigated. Reducing the number of attributes would have limited the ability to assess aspects essential to consumer perception of sustainable textiles.

For all three products, each attribute (except price) was designed to include one “standard” level, representing the conventional feature typically found in the average product available on the market, along with one or more improved alternatives, reflecting sustainable or innovative options. To enhance clarity and facilitate comprehension during the choice tasks, all improved or sustainable features were represented visually through labels. Previous studies have shown that visual representations can significantly support consumer decision-making, making it easier to identify product differences and better evaluate environmentally friendly alternatives (Aprile & Punzo, 2022; Waechter et al., 2015; Lin & Nayga, 2022).

Regarding the price attribute, the ranges were selected based on a market analysis of average price points across various European countries. The goal was to define realistic and credible price intervals that reflect actual market conditions for each product category. Price points were adjusted to remain as representative as possible of the European market, although minor deviations may persist due to country-level variability in pricing data.

- **Laundry Detergents**

In the case of detergents, attribute selection prioritized performance and environmental impact, both of which play a key role in consumer purchasing decisions. Beyond the previously defined product format, cleaning performance, specifically the ability to remove stains at low washing temperatures, was considered essential. This reflects consumer interest in effective products that also enable energy savings, aligning with broader environmental goals. Other attributes were selected to capture perceptions of sustainability, such as the type of surfactants used and the biodegradability of the formula. Particular attention was given to packaging, which was included due to its recognized importance in consumer perception of sustainability and its role in influencing product choice (Paulo et al., 2024; Hallez et al., 2024). Consumers increasingly associate recyclable and refillable packaging with lower environmental impact, making it a decisive factor in sustainable purchasing decisions. The

full list of attributes and levels for the detergent product is provided in **Figure 2** except for the prices whose levels were: €3, €4.5, €6, €7.5.

EFFICACY IN STAIN REMOVAL	RECOMMENDED WASHING TEMPERATURE	PACKAGING	SURFACTANTS
Stain removal effectiveness at recommended temperature.	Optimal stain removal temperature.	Materials used for detergent packaging.	Substances help detergents act more effectively.
Standard removal Detergent's ability to clean common stain at recommended temperature.	40-60 °C Temperature at which common detergents are most effective.	Standard plastic Packaging with a standard amount of non-recycled plastic.	Standard Use Petrochemical-based surfactants at a standard concentration.
 ECCO RENEWABLE AND SUSTAINABLE SURFACTANTS The formulation contains surfactants obtained from natural resources, such as plants or biodegradable materials.			
	 -20% SURFACTANTS IN THE FORMULATION The formulation contains 20% less petroleum-based surfactants.		

Figure 2. Banner explanation of attributes and levels for laundry detergent developed by Saija et al. [2023]. All attributes considered in the study are represented in the image, except for the price, which was also evaluated with the following levels: €3, €4.5, €6, €7.5.

- **Polyester-Based Textiles**

For textiles, the selected attributes were closely aligned with the core objectives of the FuturEnzyme project, particularly regarding the development of enzyme-treated fabrics. The study explored consumer reactions to improvements in energy and water consumption during production and reduction of chemical use. The inclusion of renewable energy aimed to assess whether consumers assign more value to a reduction in total energy consumption or to a transition to cleaner energy sources. Additionally, the analysis incorporated the release of microplastics during laundering, a topic of increasing relevance (Gliaudelytė et al., 2024, Sheikhi et al., 2024), and the fiber composition of the textile (e.g., standard polyester vs. recycled polyester), that have shown significantly influence consumer perceptions and purchase intentions (Klemm & Kaufman, 2024). The complete list of attributes and levels for the textile product is presented in **Figure 3** except for the prices whose levels were: €15, €30, €50, €70.

USE OF CHEMICALS	ENERGY CONSUPTION	WATER CONSUPTION	MATERIAL ORIGIN	MICROPLASTICS SHEDDING
Level of chemical substances used in the production of the textile product.	Amount and type of energy used during the production process.	Amount of water used during the fabric production process.	Source of the fibers used in the textile product.	Release of microplastic particles from the fabric during washing.
Standard Use of traditional chemical processes during production.	Standard Standard energy use during the production process.	Standard Standard water use during the production process.	Virgin fiber Product made of 100% virgin raw materials.	Standard Standard microplastic release, comparable to most synthetic fabrics.
 Up to 30% reduction in microplastic release.				
	 Product made of 100% recycled material.			

Figure 3. Banner explanation of attributes and levels for Polyester-Based Textiles. All attributes considered in the study are represented in the image, except for the price, which was also evaluated with the following levels: €15, €30, €50, €70.

- **Hyaluronic Acid-Based Cosmetics**

For cosmetics, the selection of attributes followed a logic similar to that used for detergents. Product effectiveness remained a central factor, reflecting consumer expectations in personal care performance.

In addition to efficacy, the growing consumer attention to ingredient origin (Wu & Liang, 2025; Shim et al., 2024) was addressed through specific levels distinguishing among different types of formulations. Packaging remained a relevant variable (Kozik et al., 2024), included here in terms of recyclability and refill ability (Kazancoglu et al., 2024). Lastly, a key sustainability indicator, the reduction of CO₂ emissions associated with the product’s production, was included as reflects one of FuturEnzyme’s key innovation goals and served to evaluate whether such environmental claims are acknowledged and valued by consumers. The attributes and levels for the cosmetic product are detailed in **Figure 4** except for the prices whose levels were: €10, €20, €40, €70.

CO ₂ EMISSIONS DURING PRODUCTION	PACKAGING	PRODUCT EFFECTIVENESS	PRODUCT INGREDIENTS
Amount of carbon dioxide (CO ₂) released into the atmosphere during the product's manufacturing process.	Type of material and design used for the product's packaging.	Perceived impact of the cosmetic product on the skin.	Type and origin of the ingredients used in cosmetic formulation.
Standard Standard CO ₂ emissions are produced.	Standard Standard packaging made from plastic or conventional materials, with no specific eco-friendly features.	Standard Provides regular skin hydration.	Standard Common ingredients without particular attention to origin, biodegradability, or ethical sourcing.
 Production methods cut emissions by 25% compared to traditional techniques.	 The packaging is made from recycled materials and/or can be recycled again after use.	 Offers more intense, longer-lasting skin hydration.	 Contains no animal-derived ingredients and is not tested on animals.
 Emissions are completely offset through environmental actions or investments in certified offset projects.	 The packaging is made from renewable, plant-based sources instead of fossil fuels.	 Improves the appearance of aging signs more effectively, with a stronger anti-aging benefit.	 Ingredients are derived from natural and renewable sources.
	 The packaging can be refilled, reducing waste.		 Ingredients break down easily and safely in the environment.

Figure 4. Banner explanation of attributes and levels for Hyaluronic Acid-Based Cosmetics. All attributes considered in the study are represented in the image, except for the price, which was also evaluated with the following levels: €10, €20, €40, €70.

Table 1 shows the list of attributes and levels for each product.

Table 1. Lists of attributes and levels for each product.

Product	Attribute	Level	Acronym	No of levels
DETERGENT	Efficacy in stain removal	Standard removal	SR	2
		Stubborn stain removal	SSR	
	Recommended washing temperature	Standard temperature (40–60 °C)	ST	3
		Save energy (30 °C)	30T	
		Maximum energy saving (20 °C)	20T	
		Standard packaging	SP	
Packaging		Recycled and recyclable plastic	RRP	3
		–70% of plastic	-70P	
Surfactants		Standard use	SS	3
		Renewable and sustainable surfactants	RSS	
Price		–20% surfactants	-20S	4
		3 €	3 €	
		4.5 €	4.5 €	
		6 €	6 €	
		7.5 €	7.5 €	

TEXTILE	Use of chemicals	Standard chemical process	SC	2
		Reduced chemicals process	RC	
	Energy consumption	Standard energy use	SE	3
		-25% energy	-25E	
		100% renewable energy	RE	
	Water consumption	Standard water use	SW	2
		-25% water consumption	-25W	
	Material origin	100% virgin fibre	100VF	3
		50% recycled material	50RF	
		100% recycled material	100RF	
Microplastics shedding	Standard microplastic release	SM	2	
	-30% microplastic release	-30M		
Price	15 €	15 €	4	
	30 €	30 €		
	50 €	50 €		
	70 €	70 €		
COSMETIC	CO ₂ emissions during production	Standard CO ₂ emissions	SCO2	3
		-25% CO ₂ emissions	-25CO2	
		Carbon neutral	NCO2	
	Packaging	Standard packaging	SP	4
		Recycled or recyclable material	RRP	
		Biobased material	BP	
		Refillable packaging	RP	
	Product effectiveness	Standard hydration	SH	3
		Deep hydration	DH	
		Enhanced anti-aging effect	EH	
	Product ingredients	Standard ingredients	SI	4
		Vegan ingredients	VI	
		Biobased ingredients	BBI	
		Biodegradable ingredients	BDI	
	Price	10 €	10 €	4
		20 €	20 €	
40 €		40 €		
70 €		70 €		

4.3.3 The Experimental Design

The Choice Experiment adopted in this study for all three product categories—laundry detergents, polyester-based textiles, and hyaluronic acid-based cosmetics—was developed using the Coordinate Exchange Algorithm (CEA), a method designed to generate statistically efficient experimental designs for stated preference surveys. The CEA works by iteratively optimizing an initial layout of the questionnaire, making stepwise improvements by modifying one attribute at a time to minimize D(B)-error, based on a multinomial logit model.

This iterative process enhances the quality and informativeness of the choice sets, ensuring that the final design enables robust data collection and reliable estimation of consumer preferences. The algorithm was implemented using the Idefix package in the R statistical environment (version 2023.12.1+402), based on adaptations of models proposed by Traets et al. (2020) and Pérez-Troncoso (2020).

By systematically exploring all combinations of attributes and levels relevant to each product category, the algorithm generated an experimental design composed of 12 choice sets for the detergent and textile and 14 choice sets for the cosmetic. Although the reference workflow (Saija et al., 2023) recommends using 8 to 9 choice sets to limit participant fatigue and reduce cognitive bias, the algorithm required a minimum of 12/14 sets to achieve a balanced and statistically efficient design. This deviation from the guidelines was

necessary to adequately reflect the complexity and number of attributes involved in the study across all three product types. While slightly above the recommended range, the final configuration was carefully reviewed to ensure that respondent comprehension and engagement were preserved, thus maintaining the validity of the results.

Each choice set presented three mutually exclusive alternatives:

- **Option A:** a product profile generated from the experimental design (product A)
- **Option B:** a product profile generated from the experimental design (product B)
- **No-choice option:** allowing respondents to select “none of the above”

The inclusion of a no-choice option aligns with best practices in CE design, as it simulates real-life decision-making conditions and enhances the external validity of the findings by allowing respondents the freedom to reject both offered products if neither was appealing.

A pilot study was conducted prior to full deployment for each product. In this phase, a zero-prior assumption was used to generate an initial design. The pilot tested the feasibility and clarity of the questionnaire, data collection procedures, and initial respondent reactions. The preliminary data obtained were then used to update the priors for the CEA algorithm, enabling a second round of optimization that produced the final design adopted for the full-scale study.

For additional technical details on the experimental design process, the reader is referred to the publication "*Assessing European Consumers' Willingness to Pay for Sustainable Laundry Detergents: A Choice Experiment Approach*" by Saija & Daniotti (2025).

4.3.4 Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire represented a key component of the study and was carefully designed to support the experimental framework while ensuring accessibility, clarity, and respondent engagement across the three product categories: laundry detergents, polyester-based textiles, and hyaluronic acid-based cosmetics.

- For the **detergent product**, the questionnaire was created using **Google Forms** and disseminated through a combination of **channels**, including emails, project website, social media platforms, and direct messaging. To maximize outreach and ensure the inclusion of diverse consumer profiles, the survey was made available in four languages: English, Spanish, German, and Italian.
- In contrast, the **textile and cosmetic questionnaires** were developed using the **Qualtrics** platform and distributed via its internal **consumer panel recruitment service**, which allowed access to a controlled and demographically segmented sample. These questionnaires were translated into six languages: English, Spanish, German, Italian, French, and Portuguese, further expanding the geographic and linguistic coverage of the study.

Participation across all product categories was voluntary and anonymous. Respondents provided informed consent before starting the questionnaire. The informed consent form included at the beginning of the survey stated:

INFORMED CONSENT

Participation

Your participation in this activity is voluntary. If you decide to take part in this study, you have the right to terminate your participation at any time without any negative consequences or penalties. The information collected will be anonymous and used exclusively for research purposes. The personal data requested will be limited to basic sociodemographic information to better analyse the responses, but confidentiality and anonymization will be ensured at any stages of the proposal.

Partner carrying out the study

*This study is carried out by **Consorzio Italbiotec**, established in Italy as part of its activities as a beneficiary of the **FuturEnzyme project (GA nr. 101000327)**.*

*For any inquiries or requests, you can contact the researchers at **presidenza@italbiotec.it***

Participant's declaration

By going on with the questionnaire, you declare the following:

- I have read and understood all the information above.
- I have voluntarily decided to participate in this research, and I am aware that I can withdraw at any stage of the project activity without being penalized or disadvantaged in any way.
- I understand that, being voluntary, I will not be paid for my participation.
- I am 18 or older.

No personal data were collected, and all responses were treated with full respect for GDPR and ethical research standards.

The questionnaire was structured into **four sections**, consistent across the three product categories:

- **Section 1 – Purchasing Choices**

This section included the 12/14 choice sets generated through the experimental design. Respondents were asked to imagine a realistic shopping scenario and to choose between two product options (Option A and Option B), each with distinct attributes and a “none of the above” (no-choice) alternative to reflect real-life purchasing behavior. Each product option was visually supported by labels highlighting key sustainability or performance features (see **Figure 1,2,3**). A representative example of a choice card is shown in **Figure 5**.

PURCHASE OPTIONS	EFFICACY IN STAIN REMOVAL	RECOMMENDED WASHING TEMPERATURE	PACKAGING	SURFACTANTS	PRICE
A	 RENEWABLE AND SUSTAINABLE SURFACTANTS	3 €			
B	Standard removal	40-60 °C	 RENEWABLE AND SUSTAINABLE SURFACTANTS	6 €	

Figure 5. Example choice card used in the study developed by Saija et al. [2023]. The card presents a hypothetical selection scenario in which respondents choose between two laundry detergent alternatives (Product A and Product B), each characterized by varying attribute levels, including price. The no-choice option, which was always available in the actual survey, is not shown in the figure. While this example refers to the laundry detergent, the same choice model and card structure were used for all three product categories evaluated in the study.

- **Section 2 – Socioeconomic and Demographic Information**

This section contained seven questions aimed at collecting key variables such as gender, age, employment status, education level, type of residence, household income, and country of residence. These data were essential for understanding how different consumer segments evaluated the attributes presented in the choice experiment.

- **Section 3 – Shopping and Usage Habits**

This section was adapted to each product type to explore both practical familiarity with the product and the consumer’s role in household purchasing decisions. Participants were asked how often they used the product, as evidence for how well they knew it and how much their evaluation could be considered based on real experience, and who was responsible for purchasing the product in their household, helping determine whether their preferences were shaped by direct buying behavior or external influence. In the case of cosmetics, an additional response option was included: “I do not know this product”, to allow respondents unfamiliar with hyaluronic acid-based products to self-identify. These responses were considered when analyzing results and interpreting data reliability.

- **Section 4 – Interest in Sustainability**

This section, identical for all three product categories, aimed to evaluate respondents’ general attitudes and awareness regarding sustainability. Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement—on

a 5-point Likert scale—with two statements related to the environmental impact of sustainable consumer products and the importance of adopting responsible purchasing behaviors. Additionally, respondents were asked to assess the relative importance of different product attributes (e.g., packaging, ingredient origin, price, biodegradability) in influencing their buying decisions. This allowed for comparison between stated preferences and observed choices in the experiment, contributing to the internal validation of the results.

4.3.5 Sample selection

The sample selection strategy differed slightly between the pilot and final phases of the study, and between the detergent, textile, and cosmetic product categories, based on the methodological objectives and the tools used for distribution.

In the pilot phase, the main goal was to test the structure, clarity, and functionality of the questionnaire, as well as the effectiveness of the experimental design. As such, no strict selection criteria were applied. The detergent pilot involved 44 respondents, predominantly Italian. Similarly, the textile pilot included 31 participants, and the cosmetic pilot involved 54 participants, both also mainly from Italy. These pilot samples were not intended to be representative of the wider population, but rather to support the refinement of the tools before launching the final studies.

In the final phase, the sample composition differed between product categories due to the methodologies used for data collection. For the detergent study, a total of 304 European responses were collected using Google Forms, which was disseminated through public channels. Since this method did not allow for control over respondent characteristics, the sample was open and non-restricted, meaning that potentially anyone who received the link could participate. As a result, no specific quotas or demographic balancing strategies were applied.

In contrast, for the textile and cosmetic studies, the surveys were distributed through the Qualtrics platform, which allowed for a more controlled recruitment process. The final sample consisted of 1031 respondents for textiles and 1019 for cosmetics. These samples were selected to be as homogeneous and balanced as possible in terms of age, gender, and geographic origin, ensuring a broad and representative cross-section of European consumers. This approach allowed for more precise segmentation and more reliable comparisons across demographic groups.

In all cases, eligibility was limited to participants aged 18 years or older.

4.3.6 Result Analysis: The Conditional Logit Model

The analytical methodology used for interpreting the results of the Choice Experiments is explained in full detail in the article *"Assessing European Consumers' Willingness to Pay for Sustainable Laundry Detergents: A Choice Experiment Approach"* by Saija & Daniotti (2025). For the purposes of this report, a concise overview is provided below.

The methodology used to analyze and interpret the data collected through the Choice Experiments is based on the Random Utility Maximization (RUM) framework. This well-established theoretical model assumes that individuals make decisions with the aim of maximizing their personal utility, and it is widely adopted in the field of discrete choice modeling, particularly in the context of Choice Experiments (CEs) (Snowball JD, 2008). This framework assumes that individuals make decisions by choosing the option that maximizes their perceived utility. Each product alternative is described through a set of attributes, and the utility it generates is composed of a deterministic component—linked to observed characteristics—and a random component that captures unobserved influences.

For the current study, the analysis was conducted using a Conditional Logit Model (CLM), implemented in R software by adapting the approach proposed by Pérez-Troncoso (2020) and Barriviera et al. (2023). The CLM is suitable for modeling discrete choices among alternatives characterized by varying attribute levels.

Additionally, Willingness to Pay (WTP) was calculated for each attribute using the ratio of the attribute coefficient to the (negative) price coefficient. This metric translates abstract preferences into a monetary value, allowing for the interpretation of how much consumers value each specific product feature. The combination of Conditional Logit estimation and WTP analysis provides a robust framework for understanding consumer preferences and the perceived value of sustainability-related product features across all three product categories investigated in this study.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Pilot Study Results

In all three pilots, the samples were gathered without applying demographic quotas, as the emphasis was on methodological testing rather than representativeness. Nevertheless, relevant sociodemographic characteristics were recorded to support the interpretation of responses and understand the familiarity of participants with the products under study.

Laundry Detergents

The detergent pilot involved a total of 44 respondents, predominantly from Italy (95%), with 61% identifying as female. The sample skewed young, with 84% under the age of 34, and was highly educated: 86% held at least a bachelor's degree. The majority of participants (89%) reported being directly responsible for detergent purchases within their household. The pilot results provided initial indications of consumer preferences, highlighting positive utilities for attributes such as stubborn stain removal, lower washing temperature (30 °C), recycled and recyclable packaging and use of renewable and sustainable surfactants.

Polyester-Based Textiles

The textile pilot included 31 participants, with 19 females and 12 males. Most respondents belonged to the Millennial generation (14) or Generation X (9), with only a small number from other age groups. The educational level was notably high, with 14 participants holding a master's degree and 9 holding a Ph.D. This profile suggests a sample of consumers with a high level of formal education and likely greater awareness of sustainability topics.

The responses indicated a generally favorable perception of environmentally responsible textile attributes. In particular, positive utility is observed for a reduction in chemicals, CO₂ emissions and water consumption during the production phase, a reduction in microplastics release, and an increase of recycled fiber in the textile composition.

Hyaluronic Acid-Based Cosmetics

The pilot study for the cosmetic product involved 44 participants, balanced in terms of gender (24 females and 20 males) and highly educated, with 25 participants holding a master's degree and 20 a Ph.D. Most respondents were either Millennials (24) or Generation X (20), while only five respondents each were classified as Boomers or Generation Z.

Given the nature of the product—based on hyaluronic acid, which may not be equally familiar to all segments—the sample composition was particularly relevant. Although most participants showed good awareness of the product type, the pilot design included a response filter to identify and account for participants who were unfamiliar with it, allowing more accurate interpretation and weighting during analysis.

Preliminary results revealed positive utility for products declared to be carbon neutral, packaging made with recycled materials, and deep hydration effect. **Outcome**

The utility coefficients derived from each pilot study were used to generate the initial priors for the experimental design, supporting the development of an efficient and realistic set of choice tasks for the final phase. The priors, although based on relatively small and non-representative samples, provided valuable early signals of consumer value perception and attribute salience. Positive utility values indicated a willingness to pay for specific improvements, while negative values highlighted features that may be less appealing to consumers. For clarity and interpretability, the coefficients were rounded to two significant digits (see **Table 2**), a practice that simplifies results without compromising analytical accuracy. These priors were then integrated into the Coordinate Exchange Algorithm (CEA) to refine the final choice set design and ensure the statistical efficiency of the models across all three product categories.

Table 2. Results of the pilot survey for the three products. The results were used to determine the priors for CEA model refinement. As the algorithm use the effect coding, one level for each attribute is removed.

	Attributes - levels	Utility (priors)
DETERGENT	No choice (alt3.cte)	- 1.98
	Standard removal	0.31
	Standard washing temperature	- 0.70
	30°C washing temperature	0.49
	4.5 €	0.97
	6 €	0.43
	7.5 €	- 0.30
	Standard plastic	- 0.58
	Recycled and recyclable packaging	0.37
	Standard use of surfactants	- 0.40
	20% reduction in the use of surfactants	- 0.16
	TEXTILE	No choice (alt3.cte)
No reduction in chemicals during production		- 0.27
No reduction in CO ₂ emissions during production		- 0.47
30% reduction in CO ₂ emissions during production		- 0.08
Standard water consumption during production		- 0.26
Standard microplastics release		- 0.51
Virgin fiber		- 0.66
50% recycled fiber		0.39
15 €		0.96
30 €		0.46
50 €		- 0.49
COSMETIC		No choice (alt3.cte)
	No reduction in CO ₂ emissions during production	- 0.73
	25% reduction in CO ₂ emissions during production	- 0.33
	Standard packaging	- 0.50
	Packaging made with recycled material	0.10
	Packaging made with bio-based material	0.02
	Standard hydration effect	- 0.77
	Deep hydration effect	0.45
	Use of standard ingredients in the formulation	- 0.79
	Use of vegan ingredients in the formulation	0.27
	Use of bio-based ingredients in the formulation	0.36
	10 €	1.18
20 €	0.51	
40 €	- 0.41	

5.2. Final Study Results and Discussion

The final version of the questionnaire developed in this study was administered across three separate surveys targeting European consumers for the evaluation of laundry detergents, polyester-based textiles, and hyaluronic acid-based cosmetics. A total of 304 respondents completed the detergent questionnaire, 1031 completed the textile version, and 1019 completed the cosmetic version.

Participants represented a diverse set of nationalities, age groups, educational backgrounds, income levels, and household compositions, ensuring a broad and meaningful analysis of consumer preferences across different population segments. The results of the respondents' profiles and their choice behaviors are presented in the following sections, structured per product category.

5.2.1 Sample's Profile Results

To facilitate clearer interpretation and allow for more robust statistical treatment, several sociodemographic categories were grouped. Age was categorized into generational cohorts: Generation Z (18–24), Millennials (25–34), Generation X (35–54), and Boomers (55+). Employment status was aggregated into two broad groups: employed (including both employees and self-employed individuals) and unemployed (including students, retirees, and unemployed individuals). Regarding education, three levels were considered: Diplomas (including no formal title, high school diploma, and higher education diploma), Master's degrees (including both master's and second-level postgraduate master's), and Highest education (including Ph.D. and postgraduate specialization programs).

These simplifications enabled meaningful segmentation and clearer interpretation of the data across different product samples. **Table 3** provides a summary of the key descriptive statistics for each of the three product categories, allowing cross-comparison.

Table 3. Results of the socioeconomic and demographic information section of the questionnaire for the three products.

Variable	Range	Frequency Detergent	Frequency Textile	Frequency Cosmetic
Age	18-24	43	256	254
	25-34	106	258	252
	35-44	58	125	125
	45-54	35	134	131
	55-64	45	143	150
	65+	17	113	107
Gender	Female	197	516	515
	Male	107	510	499
	Other	0	4	4
	I choose not to answer	0	1	1
Employment	Employee	200	549	568
	Self-employed ¹	18	96	78
	Unemployed ²	8	108	112
	Retired	21	144	133
	Student	57	134	128
Education	No title	3	65	52
	High School Diploma ³	58	335	348
	Higher Education Diploma	4	320	208
	Bachelor's degree	61	209	217
	Master's Degree	94	114	116
	Second-Level Postgraduate Master's	2	40	35
	Ph.D.	81	29	33
Postgraduate Specialization Course	1	9	10	
Annual household income	< 20,000.00 €	47	266	261
	20,000€ - 40,000€	105	341	353
	40,000€ - 60,000€	64	215	186

	60,000€ - 80,000€	40	98	108
	> 80,000€	48	111	111
Residence Type	Private home (rented or owned)	107	363	410
	Apartment (rented or owned)	135	434	395
	Apartment shared with students	20	37	15
	University residence	6	39	27
	Living with parents	36	158	172
	Country	Italy	129	103
Spain		79	104	103
Belgium		2	103	102
France		1	102	102
Ireland		0	105	101
Germany		35	103	102
Portugal		23	103	103
UK		9	100	101
Sweden		7	0	0
Switzerland		5	103	103
Austria		3	103	103
Others		5	1	1
Non-European countries ⁵		4	1	0

¹Both entrepreneurs and households are included in this category

²Included within this category are housewives

³Both technical and educational degrees are included in this category

⁴This category includes countries that are not included in the list.

⁵This category includes Russia, USA, New Zealand and Zambia.

The recruitment of participants followed two distinct approaches depending on the product category. For the detergent sample (n = 304), responses were collected through open-access distribution, using public links shared via digital channels. This method allowed for broad participation but without control over the demographic balance of the sample. In contrast, the textile (n = 1031) and cosmetic (n = 1019) samples were obtained through structured panel recruitment via the Qualtrics platform, which enabled the application of balanced quotas based on age, gender, and geographic origin, ensuring demographic representativeness across the European consumer population.

To guarantee clarity and full comprehension of the questionnaire, the panel was limited to respondents from countries where one of the six available languages—Italian, Spanish, French, German, English, and Portuguese—is commonly spoken as a native language. As a result, participants were recruited only from Italy, Spain, Belgium, France, Ireland, Germany, Portugal, the United Kingdom, Sweden, Switzerland, and Austria. This strategy minimized potential misunderstandings due to language barriers and ensured greater reliability in the interpretation of product attributes and sustainability concepts.

Laundry Detergents

The detergent sample (n = 304) was collected through open-access distribution channels and thus reflects a broad, though uncontrolled, demographic distribution. Despite the absence of quota-based recruitment, the sample captured considerable diversity in terms of gender, age, education, and geography. The population is primarily composed of Millennials (34.9%) and Generation X (30.6%), with lower representation of Boomers (20.4%) and Generation Z (14.1%). This age distribution reflects a relatively young sample, likely to be active in household purchasing decisions.

Women constituted 64.8% of the sample, suggesting a gender imbalance that may influence preference trends, especially in a product category like laundry detergent where women often play a leading role in household decision-making.

The employment profile shows a predominance of working individuals (71.7%), followed by a significant share of students (18.75%), indicating an overall active and professionally engaged respondent base. This may impact on attitudes toward sustainability and willingness to pay, as employed consumers typically have greater purchasing autonomy.

The educational level of the sample is notably high. Nearly one-third of respondents (30.9%) reported holding a master's degree, and an additional 26.6% had attained the highest education levels, including Ph.D. or postgraduate specializations. This academic background suggests a capacity to understand and evaluate complex product information, such as ingredient origin, environmental certifications, or biodegradability.

As for household income, the most common income range reported was €20,000–€40,000 (34.5%), with a substantial proportion falling into higher brackets. This distribution indicates a middle-to-upper class socioeconomic profile, consistent with high education and employment rates. Housing data show that the majority of respondents (79.6%) live in private homes or apartments, while 8.6% reside in shared or student housing, suggesting a population characterized by independent living arrangements.

Geographically, the sample is mostly European, though not evenly distributed. The highest concentration of respondents was from Italy (42.4%), followed by Spain (26%) and Germany (11.5%). Smaller shares came from Portugal (7.6%), the United Kingdom (3%), and other countries. Non-European responses made up just 1.3%, confirming the European focus of the study.

In summary, the detergent sample reflects a relatively young, predominantly female, highly educated, and economically stable population, mostly residing in European countries. These characteristics should be taken into account when interpreting consumer preferences and willingness to pay for sustainability features in laundry products.

Polyester-Based Textiles

The textile sample (n = 1031), by contrast, was recruited through a structured panel (Qualtrics) using the Qualtrics platform, which allowed for the application of balanced quotas by age, gender, and geographical origin. This approach ensured that the sample was more evenly distributed and demographically representative of the European consumer population.

In terms of gender, the sample was 50.0% female, 49.5% male, with an additional 0.4% identifying as non-binary or other, and 0.1% preferring not to disclose. This near parity between men and women enables an equitable analysis of potential gender-based differences in the valuation of sustainability-related textile attributes. Given that the selected product was a unisex T-shirt, this balance helps prevent skewed insights due to gender-specific usage patterns.

Regarding age distribution, the sample was 24.8% Generation Z (18–24), 25.0% Millennials (25–34), 25.1% Generation X (35–54), and 25.0% Boomers (55+). This almost perfectly even segmentation across generations is particularly valuable for capturing possible generational differences in sustainability awareness, price sensitivity, and product expectations. It also allows for the analysis of how environmental preferences evolve across life stages.

As for employment status, 62.6% of respondents were employed (either as employees or self-employed), while 37.4% were not employed, including students, retirees, and unemployed individuals. This variable is key to understanding potential differences in willingness to pay (WTP). Employed respondents may exhibit greater financial flexibility, possibly leading to a higher valuation of improved or sustainable attributes, while

non-employed individuals may be more constrained in their trade-offs between cost and environmental impact.

The educational level of the sample was notably high. As shown in Table 3, more than half of the respondents had completed tertiary education. Only 6.3% of respondents had no formal educational title. This composition reflects a relatively well-educated sample, which is likely to influence both awareness of sustainability-related issues and interpretation of environmental claims such as eco-labels, fiber origin, or microplastic emissions. Well-educated consumers are often more receptive to technical information, which may lead to more informed and structured decision-making patterns during the CE. Furthermore, the presence of a large group with university or postgraduate qualifications increases the likelihood that respondents are already familiar with concepts like circular economy, environmental impact of production processes, and certifications, potentially amplifying the sensitivity of the sample to certain sustainability attributes presented in the textile scenarios.

In terms of household income, the sample revealed a concentration in the low-to-middle-income brackets. Approximately 25.8% of respondents reported earning less than €20,000 annually, while 33.0% declared an income between €20,000 and €40,000. About 20.8% fell into the €40,000–€60,000 range, with 9.5% between €60,000 and €80,000, and 10.8% earning more than €80,000. This distribution indicates that a significant portion of the sample, more than half, may be relatively sensitive to price when evaluating product alternatives. At the same time, the presence of higher-income respondents offers the opportunity to assess how disposable income influences willingness to pay for sustainability attributes such as certified production, energy-efficient manufacturing, or the use of recycled fibers.

Lastly, the geographic distribution of the sample—enabled using a structured consumer panel—was evenly spread across ten European countries: Italy, Spain, Belgium, France, Ireland, Germany, Portugal, the United Kingdom, Sweden, Switzerland, and Austria. This homogeneity strengthens the cross-country comparability of preferences and supports broader generalizations about European consumer behavior in the textile sector.

This well-balanced sociodemographic and geographic composition provides a solid foundation for interpreting consumer preferences and supports the robustness and external validity of the results obtained through the Choice Experiment.

Hyaluronic Acid-Based Cosmetics

The **cosmetic sample** (n = 1019) shares similar structural characteristics, having also been collected through the same panel approach. The gender distribution is balanced, with 50.5% female, 49.0% male, 0.4% who preferred not to respond, and 0.1% identifying as other. This balanced distribution allows for the analysis of gender-based differences in cosmetic preferences, which is particularly relevant given the historical predominance of women in the cosmetics market and the increasing visibility of male consumers in this sector.

The age composition is nearly identical to the textile sample, with Generation Z, Millennials, Generation X, and Boomers each accounting for roughly 25% of the population. This segmentation enables detailed investigation into how preferences for sustainability attributes vary across age cohorts with different exposure to cosmetic use and environmental awareness.

Regarding employment status, 63.4% of respondents declared they were employed, while 36.6% were not employed, including students, retirees, and unemployed individuals. More than 60% of respondents in the cosmetic sample reported a household income below €40,000 per year. This distinction is particularly important when interpreting price sensitivity and willingness to pay, especially for cosmetic products, where sustainability may be perceived as an added value or a luxury.

The educational background of the sample reveals a generally high level of formal education. A significant portion of participants completed secondary or post-secondary education, and many held a bachelor's or master's degree. A smaller but meaningful group had also completed Ph.D. or postgraduate specialization programs. Only a small percentage of respondents reported having no formal qualification. This profile suggests a general ability to understand and assess complex product attributes.

As expected from a controlled panel distribution, geographic representation across the selected countries was even and aligned with language availability, supporting the consistency and clarity of responses.

In conclusion, the three samples present different characteristics based on the recruitment method. The detergent sample reflects a younger, female-skewed, and academically advanced group, but with a less controlled geographic spread. In contrast, the textile and cosmetic samples are demographically balanced and geographically representative, enabling robust cross-country and subgroup analyses. Together, these profiles form a solid foundation for the interpretation of choice behavior and sustainability preferences in the following sections.

5.2.2. Consumer Habits and Preferences in Sustainability

Laundry Detergents

The evaluation of consumer habits provided clear insights into **laundry behavior** among respondents. Just under 55% indicated that they typically carry out 2 to 3 laundry cycles per week, while a considerable 24% reported doing 0 to 1 cycle weekly. Combined, these two groups represent around 80% of the sample, suggesting that most participants follow relatively moderate laundry routines. However, the higher end of this range—namely the 2–3 cycles per week—still indicates potential for improvement in terms of reducing water and energy consumption, especially from a sustainability perspective.

Another relevant finding concerns consumer engagement in household purchasing. Approximately 85% of respondents stated they are actively involved in detergent purchase decisions, which highlights the relevance and reliability of their input. This level of involvement suggests that participants are well-informed about the detergent market and aware of their preferences regarding product features, adding weight to the survey's findings.

In terms of attitudes toward sustainability, responses to two targeted questions revealed strong consumer support for environmentally conscious behavior. About 82% of participants indicated that they consider the transition to more sustainable consumer products as “somewhat” or “very” important in addressing climate change. Likewise, 88% expressed the view that adopting more responsible purchasing habits is a key factor in promoting sustainability.

Polyester-Based Textiles

Related to the polyester-based textile product, the sample revealed equally informative consumer behavior patterns. Just over 28.9% of respondents stated that they use this type of fabric 1–2 times per week, while 28.6% reported using it more than 3 times weekly. This means that nearly 57.5% of the sample interacts with the product on a regular basis, offering a strong foundation for evaluating preferences based on actual usage experience. Additionally, 17.9% of respondents indicated they use it occasionally (a couple of times per week), reinforcing the relevance of their responses. On the other hand, approximately 24.4% of the sample reported rarely using this type of textile, and 10.8% stated they do not use it at all, suggesting a smaller but notable share of participants whose responses may be influenced more by general perceptions than by direct product familiarity.

In terms of attribute relevance, 40.7% of participants identified price as the most important factor when buying clothing. This result is not surprising, as apparel is a frequently purchased good and often evaluated

under budget constraints. Conversely, the use of chemical substances in textile production was considered the least important attribute by 32.3% of respondents. This lower prioritization could stem from a lack of visibility or understanding of chemical impacts in textile manufacturing, highlighting a potential gap in consumer knowledge and suggesting that more technical attributes may require better communication to be fully appreciated by consumers.

Sustainability perceptions within the textile sample were also highly positive. 73.8% of respondents agreed that making consumer products more sustainable is among the most impactful strategies for reducing global environmental harm. A nearly identical proportion—71.5%—recognized the consumer's role in shaping environmental outcomes through their purchasing choices.

Hyaluronic Acid-Based Cosmetics

In the case of hyaluronic acid-based cosmetics, the analysis of consumer responses reveals some interesting and at times unexpected patterns regarding both product usage and attribute perception.

Consumers identified packaging as the most important attribute influencing their purchasing decisions. This result likely reflects the strong visual and tangible nature of packaging, which is often perceived as the most immediate and visible component of a product's environmental impact. For many consumers, sustainable packaging may signal a clear and direct effort toward reducing waste or using recyclable materials, unlike other attributes that are less observable or more complex to interpret. Surprisingly, product efficacy was reported as the least important attribute by a significant share of respondents, even if efficacy is typically considered a core factor in evaluating personal care products. This contradiction may indicate that some respondents did not respond fully sincerely to this section of the survey, possibly due to social desirability bias. It is also possible that sustainability momentarily overshadows functional expectations, despite the latter being essential for product satisfaction.

Regarding product familiarity, the sample presents a notable split. On one side, 468 individuals (45.9%) declared they use the product at least once a day or several times a day, suggesting a strong familiarity and habitual engagement with hyaluronic acid-based cosmetics. On the other side, approximately 277 respondents (27.2%) reported that they rarely use or are not familiar with the product at all, indicating a considerable share of the sample with limited direct experience. Notably, among those unfamiliar with the product, a large majority (173 out of 277) were male, reinforcing the idea that gender may still influence familiarity with certain cosmetic product types, although a significant number of women also reported low familiarity. Despite these differences, the sample is demographically homogeneous and well-distributed, which contributes to the representativeness and interpretability of the results. Additionally, 875 participants (85.9%) reported being involved in the purchasing process for this type of product, further validating the relevance of their stated preferences.

In terms of sustainability perceptions, the cosmetic sample – as other samples – reflects strong environmental awareness. A majority of the 70.8% of respondents agreed that making consumer products more sustainable is among the most impactful strategies to mitigate global environmental impact. A nearly equivalent share—72.7%—acknowledged the critical role of consumers in shaping this impact through their choices. These findings reinforce the idea that while product familiarity and attribute importance may vary, the underlying environmental values are consistently present across the sample.

5.2.3. Respondents' Preferences for products Purchasing

The results of the respondents' preferences, based on CLM, have been evaluated first on the entire sample and then by making distinctions between different sociodemographic categories in order to assess specific drivers in different categories.

Laundry Detergents

The results of the Choice Experiment (**Table 4**) provide clear evidence that European consumers are willing to pay a premium for sustainable detergent attributes, with particular emphasis on environmental impact and product performance. Notably, the estimated willingness to pay (WTP) for enhanced stain removal efficacy amounts to €1.54, indicating that product effectiveness remains a key determinant in consumer purchasing decisions. This outcome is consistent with previous research findings, which highlight the persistent importance attributed to functional performance, as consumers are generally reluctant to compromise on this aspect. However, it is important to note that effectiveness does not represent the attribute associated with the highest WTP premium. Instead, the analysis reveals a stronger consumer preference and greater willingness to invest in sustainability-related features, underscoring the growing relevance of environmental considerations in consumer choice behavior.

Table 4. Willingness to pay (WTP) for each attribute according to socioeconomic and demographic information. SSR= Stubborn Stain Removal; 30T = 30°C washing temperature; 20T = 20°C washing temperature; RRP = recycled and recyclable plastics; -70P= -70% plastics; RSS = renewable and sustainable surfactants; -20S = -20% surfactants.

Sample	SSR	30T	20T	RRP	-70P	RSS	-20S
Total	+1.54€	+1.85€	+1.54€	+2.11€	+2.42€	+2.23€	+1.42€
Italy	+1.46€	+1.70€	+1.29€	+1.82€	+2.31€	+2.13€	+1.45€
Spain	+2.23€	+2.57€	+2.49€	+2.91€	+3.49€	+3.04€	+2.05€
Germany	+1.24€	+2.00€	+1.39€	+2.31€	+2.25€	+1.77€	+1.10€
Portugal	+1.01 €	+1.42€	+1.52€	+1.56€	+2.09€	+1.96€	+1.05€
Generation Z	+1.50€	+1.57€	+1.27€	+2.08€	+2.03€	+2.18€	+1.02€
Millennials	+1.24€	+1.70€	+1.20€	+1.69€	+1.76€	+1.81€	+1.06€
Generation X	+1.66€	+2.06€	+1.76€	+2.42€	+3.31€	+2.40€	+1.79€
Boomers	+2.49€	+2.59€	+2.67€	+2.74€	+2.99€	+3.67€	+2.69€
Employed	+1.48€	+1.91€	+1.61€	+2.07€	+2.51€	+2.33€	+1.50€
Unemployed	+1.68€	+1.69€	+1.37€	+2.19€	+2.21€	+1.96€	+1.21€
Diploma	+1.70€	+1.47€	+0.96€	+2.32€	+2.65€	+2.68€	+1.48€
Bachelor	+1.46€	+1.91€	+1.86€	+2.35€	+2.57€	+2.39€	+1.44€
Master	+1.41€	+1.43€	+1.08€	+1.74€	+1.73€	+1.69€	+0.99€
PhD	+2.28€	+2.47€	+0.18€	-2.5€	-0.97€	+1.68€	+0.80€
Male	+1.56€	+1.87€	+1.69€	+1.84€	+2.13€	+1.94€	+1.38€
Female	+1.52€	+1.83	+1.44	+2.26	+2.55	+2.36	+1.43
< 20.000€	+0.98€	+1.30€	+1.37€	+1.82€	+1.74€	+1.74€	+1.21€
20.000€ - 40.000€	+1.39€	+1.76€	+1.08€	+1.81€	+2.07€	+1.94€	+1.23€
40.000€ - 60.000€	+1.84€	+1.61€	+1.48€	+2.45€	+2.73€	+2.57€	+1.50€
60.000€ - 80.000€	+2.10€	+3.03€	+2.82€	+2.84€	+4.33€	+3.97€	+2.40€
> 80.000€	+1.70€	+2.21€	+2.21€	+2.30€	+2.55€	+2.17€	+1.37€

The highest willingness to pay (WTP) values emerged for attributes associated with product sustainability. Specifically, a 70% reduction in plastic packaging generated a WTP premium of €2.42, while the use of renewable and sustainable surfactants in the product formulation was valued at €2.22. Within the packaging domain, consumers showed a clear preference for reducing plastic content over merely employing recycled

or recyclable materials. This suggests that the total elimination or minimization of plastic is perceived as a more tangible and credible environmental commitment.

In the case of surfactants, the WTP for renewable and sustainable alternatives was nearly double that of a basic reduction in surfactant quantity—showing a differential of €0.80. This disparity may indicate a greater perceived environmental value or emotional resonance associated with renewable surfactants. Moreover, it is plausible that consumers perceive a reduction in surfactant quantity as potentially compromising product effectiveness, whereas renewable surfactants offer a solution that aligns both with ecological responsibility and performance expectations.

Attributes related to washing temperature were associated with comparatively lower willingness to pay (WTP) values, indicating that consumers tend to prioritize other product characteristics over the potential energy savings derived from lower temperature washing cycles. Specifically, respondents demonstrated a higher WTP for effective washing at 30 °C compared to 20 °C, with a differential of approximately €0.30. This pattern may suggest limited consumer confidence in the efficacy of cold washing, even when equivalent performance is guaranteed. These findings imply that although consumers may recognize the environmental and economic advantages of lower washing temperatures, such benefits appear to be less compelling than more tangible and perceptible sustainability attributes—such as reduced plastic usage or the inclusion of renewable ingredients.

The results offer a nuanced understanding of the drivers behind consumer preferences. Sustainability-related attributes, particularly those that are visible, emotionally resonant, or clearly differentiated, emerge as dominant factors in purchasing decisions. In some instances, these attributes even outweigh traditional determinants such as product effectiveness, highlighting the evolving nature of consumer values in the context of sustainable consumption.

However, an interesting contradiction arises when comparing these WTP values to survey responses on the most and least important attributes. While nearly 50% of respondents identified effectiveness as the most important factor (followed by price at 28%), over 41% considered packaging the least relevant, followed by surfactants (27%). These results are inconsistent with the WTP data, where packaging and surfactants received the highest premiums, even exceeding effectiveness. This discrepancy likely reflects the divergence between stated preferences (derived from direct survey responses) and revealed preferences (inferred from hypothetical choice behavior). One plausible explanation is that when explicitly questioned, respondents prioritize traditionally rational criteria such as effectiveness and cost, aligning with conventional consumer logic. However, in choice-based scenarios that simulate real-world purchasing conditions, consumers appear to be more influenced—consciously or subconsciously—by attributes associated with sustainability. These may resonate more deeply with personal values or broader environmental concerns. This phenomenon could also be attributed to the well-documented attitude–intention–behavior gap (Wijekoon & Sabri, 2021; Chainhanchai P., 2023; Sharma AP, 2021), which refers to the discrepancy between the stated values of an individual or organization and their actual actions. While consumers may genuinely express a preference for attributes such as effectiveness and price in explicit surveys, their willingness to pay premiums for sustainability-related features in purchasing scenarios highlights a divergence between their articulated priorities and the choices they make when ethical or emotional considerations come into play. For example, an overlooked but relevant factor in detergent preference is fragrance, which was not included among the evaluated attributes in this study. Fragrance, though not directly linked to sustainability, significantly affects user satisfaction and product acceptance, particularly among female consumers, who constitute the majority of the sample. While not directly related to sustainability, a detergent’s fragrance can strongly influence perceived quality and satisfaction and may act as a barrier to the adoption of more sustainable alternatives if it fails to meet consumer expectations.

Furthermore, the relatively lower WTP for product effectiveness compared to sustainability attributes may also be influenced by a 'baseline assumption' bias (Ebbing T, 2022). This cognitive bias suggests that consumers implicitly assume a minimum standard of effectiveness across all detergent products and, as a result, are less willing to pay an additional premium for this feature. In contrast, sustainability-related attributes are often perceived as added-value elements or differentiating factors.

The analysis of socioeconomic and demographic aspects revealed generational differences in WTP for sustainable product attributes. Generational differences in WTP were significant: Baby Boomers exhibited the highest willingness to pay across most attributes, balancing both effectiveness and sustainability. This was somewhat surprising, given the commonly held assumption that younger generations are more environmentally conscious. However, it is likely explained by greater financial stability and purchasing power among older consumers. Income-stratified analysis further supports this interpretation: WTP was positively correlated with income, particularly above the €60,000 threshold, where respondents demonstrated the highest premiums for reduced plastic packaging (€+4.33) and renewable surfactants (€+3.97). These findings suggest that consumers with higher purchasing power—often older individuals—are more capable of facing the additional cost associated with environmentally friendly products.

Interestingly, those earning more than €80,000 showed slightly lower WTP across all attributes. This discrepancy is likely due to the smaller sample size in this income category, making the results less representative. In contrast, younger consumers—Millennials and Generation Z—although expressing strong support for sustainability, demonstrated lower WTP overall, likely due to more limited financial resources, which constrain their ability to align preferences with actions. Overall, the findings underscore a critical dynamic: those most willing to pay for sustainability are also those with higher financial stability, reinforcing the idea that affordability emerges as a key moderating factor in the translation of environmental awareness into consumer action.

The results show that education level affects willingness to pay (WTP) for sustainability-related product features, but in an unexpected way. Participants with a diploma or bachelor's degree reported the highest WTP for sustainable attributes. In comparison, those with a master's degree showed more moderate values, and Ph.D. holders had the lowest WTP—sometimes even negative—for certain features like recycled packaging. This is in contrast with the common belief that higher education leads to stronger environmental awareness and a greater willingness to pay for eco-friendly products. One possible reason is that people with more advanced education tend to be more critical when evaluating sustainability claims. They may be more aware of greenwashing—when companies overstate their environmental efforts—which can lead to more skepticism and lower WTP.

On the other hand, individuals with lower or moderate levels of education may be more influenced by sustainability messaging and marketing, perceiving sustainable attributes as a unique value proposition that justifies a higher price. It's also important to note that the lower and more variable WTP among Ph.D. respondents could be partly due to the small number of people in this group. A smaller sample can lead to less reliable results, so these findings should be interpreted with caution.

Gender-based differences in willingness to pay (WTP) were consistent with well-documented patterns in sustainable consumer behavior. Female respondents showed a higher WTP for attributes such as sustainable packaging and the use of renewable surfactants. This tendency may reflect both traditional and current gender roles, where women are often the primary decision-makers for household products and are generally more sensitive to social and environmental issues. These findings are in line with previous research in consumer behavior, which consistently shows that women tend to express stronger pro-environmental attitudes and are more likely to act on them than men (Plavsic S, 2013; Tien & Huang, 2023; Li et al., 2022) []. Male respondents, by contrast, exhibited slightly higher WTP for features related to energy efficiency, such

as effective washing at lower temperatures. This may reflect a greater interest in technical performance and cost savings, aligning with traditional male preferences for practicality and efficiency.

These gender-specific patterns, alongside generational and income-based differences, provide important insights into designing targeted marketing strategies. Tailoring communication and product positioning to reflect the values and priorities of different demographic groups can help increase engagement and improve the adoption of sustainable products.

From a geographical perspective, the results show that national context plays an important role in shaping willingness to pay (WTP) for sustainable product features. Spanish consumers reported the highest WTP values across nearly all attributes—especially for reduced plastic packaging and renewable surfactants. This may be influenced by strong public sustainability campaigns and supportive policy frameworks in Spain. Italian and German respondents followed similar trends but with more moderate WTP values. In contrast, Portuguese consumers showed the lowest WTP, which may reflect economic limitations or a lower emphasis on sustainability in everyday purchasing decisions.

In summary, the analysis confirms that reduced plastic packaging and renewable surfactants are the most influential factors driving consumer choices in sustainable detergents. These are followed by product performance and energy efficiency. However, the data also reveals significant variation in WTP across different income levels, education backgrounds, age groups, genders, and countries. This suggests that the adoption of sustainable products depends on a complex combination of values, habits, expectations, and financial means. For companies and policymakers, these findings highlight the need for targeted communication and pricing strategies. Adapting messages and product offerings to the specific needs and preferences of different consumer groups will be key to encouraging widespread adoption of sustainable products.

This study presents several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results and that offer valuable guidance for future research.

A key limitation concerns the exclusion of fragrance as an attribute in the choice experiment. Fragrance plays a significant role in consumer perception of detergents, particularly among female respondents, who constituted the majority of the sample. Although not directly linked to sustainability, scent is strongly associated with perceived quality, cleanliness, and product satisfaction. Its omission may have unintentionally shifted respondents' attention toward other attributes, potentially inflating the relative importance of sustainability features. Moreover, traditional expectations such as fragrance could continue to act as barriers to the adoption of sustainable alternatives if not adequately addressed. The lack of sensory attributes, therefore, limits the study's ability to fully capture emotional and experiential drivers of consumer choice. Future research should consider incorporating such dimensions to better reflect real-world decision-making processes.

The study also has demographic and geographic constraints. The sample was primarily composed of consumers from four European countries—Spain, Italy, Germany, and Portugal—while other EU nations were underrepresented. This limits the broader generalizability of the findings across Europe. A more geographically diverse and balanced sample would provide a more accurate understanding of pan-European preferences.

Additionally, certain subgroups were underrepresented, particularly individuals with annual incomes above €80,000 and those with a PhD. The small sample sizes in these categories reduce the reliability and statistical power of the insights derived from these groups, especially where WTP estimates appeared inconsistent or highly variable.

Future studies should aim to address these limitations by:

- Including sensory attributes such as fragrance to capture emotional and affective dimensions of consumer choice.
- Expanding the geographical scope to ensure a more representative sample of European consumers.
- Ensuring adequate representation across all income and education levels to enhance the robustness and applicability of the findings.

Polyester-Based Textiles

The findings from the Choice Experiment for the polyester-based textile product reveal a strong consumer preference for sustainability-related attributes, particularly those tied to energy and water efficiency and microplastic reduction. Among the total sample, the highest willingness to pay (WTP) was recorded for attributes such as 50% recycled fibers in textile composition (€+15.37), followed by 30% reduction in microplastic release (€+8.91) and 25% reduction in energy consumption (€+8.38). A reduction in water consumption and in the use of chemicals during textile production is also associated with positive WTP in the total sample (+4.2€ and +5.5€, respectively). These values clearly indicate that consumers place significant value on tangible environmental improvements, especially when they are easily understood. In contrast, standard usage levels for chemicals, energy, water, and microplastics as well as the use of virgin material in the textile composition were associated with negative WTP values—€-5.5, €-7.75, €-4.2, €-8.91 and €-9.54 respectively—reflecting a clear aversion to traditional, non-sustainable practices. Different from the detergent results, the attributes prioritization that emerge from the WTP analysis is overall aligned with survey responses on the most and least important attributes. In particular, the use of chemical substances in textile production, which was considered the least important attribute, shows also a low WTP compared to other factors.

Interestingly, the WTP associated with a textile composed of 100% recycled material shows a negative WTP (-5.83€), although higher than the virgin material. This suggests that consumers understand the environmental impact of reducing the use of virgin material in textile products but at the same time they are not entirely convinced of the desirability of fully recycled materials in clothing. Indeed, consumers may associate 100% recycled materials with lower quality, particularly in terms of softness, durability, or overall performance and, at the same time, they may be skeptical about whether the claim is accurate. This contrast highlights the need to better communicate the benefits of the recycling process, providing accurate claims, possibly supported or certified by third parties, in terms of sustainability as well as quality and performance testing of the final product.

Demographic analysis further highlights meaningful differences in WTP. Gender plays a significant role, with female respondents reporting higher WTP values for reduced energy consumptions, particularly a €+10.33 premium for reduced energy consumption, while maintaining positive WTP for all other sustainability attributes. However, male respondents, despite showing a lower WTP for reduced energy consumption (+5.97€), showed consistently higher WTP for other green attributes, mainly 50% recycled content (+17.84€) and reduction of microplastics release (+10.36€). Although literature generally suggests that women are more engaged in sustainable consumption, these data reveal a more nuanced reality: both genders value sustainability but are influenced by different dimensions—women by conservation-related features, and men by material innovation and environmental impact. These insights highlight the importance of tailoring sustainability messaging to align with gender-specific priorities and perceptions.

Age-based patterns were also significant. Generation Z reported an exceptionally high WTP across the majority sustainability attributes, including €+21.32 for 50% recycled textile and €+13.29 for energy reduction, indicating a strong environmental orientation among younger consumers. They even valued positively the use of renewable energy in the production (€+2.46) in contrast with the total sample. Interestingly, GenZ showed the lowest WTP for a reduction in the use of chemicals, suggesting that they may

associated “chemical-free” with compromised performance or that they may recognize that not all chemicals are inherently harmful, and that proper treatment and management can mitigate their environmental impact. For the attributes “reduced microplastics” and “50% recycled material,” a clear age-related decline in WTP is observed, with Baby Boomers reporting the lowest values at €+7.06 and €+10.27, respectively. This trend suggests that younger generations, particularly Gen Z and Millennials, are more attuned to pollution and material circularity, possibly reflecting stronger alignment with recent sustainability narratives. In contrast, other attributes do not follow a consistent generational pattern. For instance, Millennials exhibited a negative WTP for reduced water consumption (€-2.52), indicating that water conservation may not be a strong purchase driver for this group. Interestingly, Gen X showed the highest WTP for reduced chemical use (€+9.59), suggesting that this generation may place greater value on safety and health-related improvements, possibly due to heightened concern for product impact on personal or family well-being.

Income-based analysis confirmed the expected relationship between financial capacity and willingness to invest in sustainable alternatives. Respondents in the €60,000–80,000 bracket recorded the highest WTP values across key attributes, particularly €+11.8 for reduced chemical use, €+11.87 for reduced microplastics and €+21.8 for clothes with 50% recycled content. Interestingly, a non-linear pattern emerges when comparing middle-income groups: respondents in the €20,000–40,000 bracket demonstrated higher WTP for certain attributes than those in the €40,000–60,000 group, such as CO₂ emission reduction (€+14.39 vs €+4.99) and water conservation (€+5.21 vs €+1.98). This suggests that environmental values may sometimes override financial limitations, especially among more sustainability-conscious segments of lower-middle income earners. At the higher end of the spectrum, individuals earning above €80,000 showed slightly lower WTP values overall, which may reflect sample size limitations, or perhaps a greater emphasis on premium quality, brand reputation, or other non-environmental product attributes in higher income levels.

National differences were also prominent and provide insights into the role of cultural and policy contexts. Considering the main countries targeted by the FuturEnzyme project, German consumers showed the highest overall WTP for a reduction in the use of chemicals (€+17.61), water consumption (€+15.68), microplastics (€+18.03) as well as the use of 50% recycled material (+€20.22) a 25% reduction in energy consumption (€+30.54), water consumption (€+25.03), and microplastic release (€+17.2). This could reflect heightened awareness driven by national sustainability initiatives or a cultural alignment with environmental responsibility. Portuguese respondents also exhibited strong WTP, with values such as €+30.54 for reduced energy consumption. Italian and Spanish consumers followed similar patterns, albeit with more moderate values, suggesting a shared but less intense prioritization of sustainability. In contrast, Swiss respondents showed the lowest WTP across all sustainability attributes, while showing a positive and high WTP for the use of 100% renewable energy in textile production (€+4.52). This polarization may reflect a more critical or selective interpretation of sustainability claims or a preference for quality and performance over environmental impact.

The cumulative results point to several key insights. First, consumers show the highest willingness to pay for clear and tangible sustainability features, such as 50% recycled content, microplastic reduction, and energy savings. Other attributes like water and chemical reduction are also valued, but to a lesser extent. Second, preferences vary across demographic groups: women prioritize resource efficiency, while men are more responsive to material-related features. Age also matters—younger generations, especially Gen Z, are more engaged with most green attributes, although they assign lower value to chemical reduction, possibly due to concerns about product performance or a more informed view of chemical management. Income influences WTP as expected, but middle-income groups often show stronger support for sustainability than both lower and higher income brackets. Lastly, national context plays a strong role: German and Portuguese consumers

lead in WTP, while Swiss consumers are more selective, valuing only certain attributes like renewable energy use.

A few technical limitations should however be taken into consideration for this study. Indeed, the CE design focused primarily on sustainability-related attributes, but in the textile sector, aesthetics, brand, comfort, and fit play a critical role in purchase decisions. By excluding these, the study may overestimate the weight of sustainability in the actual decision process. Additionally, as the negative WTP for 100% recycled material show, some of the sustainability attributes included—such as chemical reduction, microplastic release, or carbon neutrality—may not be fully understood by all respondents, especially in a textile context, leading to inconsistent or misinformed choice behavior, and possibly under- or overvaluation of certain features.

In summary, despite its limitations, this study confirms that most consumers are willing to pay more for sustainable textiles, but their choices depend on how they understand and value different attributes (**Table 5**). To succeed, companies and policymakers should tailor communication and product strategies to the specific expectations of different demographic and national groups.

Table 5. Willingness to pay (WTP) for each attribute according to socioeconomic and demographic information. For the country-specific analysis, only the countries in which the partners are based are shown. RC = Reduced chemicals; -25E = -25% in energy consumption; RE= renewable energy; -25W = -25% in water consumption; -30M = -30% in microplastics release; 100VF= 100%virging fiber; 50RF = 50% recycled fiber; 100RF = 100% recycled fiber.

Sample	RC	-25E	RE	-25W	-30M	100VF	50RF	100RF
Total	+5.5€	+8.38€	-0.36€	+4.2€	+8.91€	-9.54€	+15.37€	-5.83€
Italy	+1.36€	+3.91€	+1.88€	+9.26€	+9.26€	-5.41€	+12.71€	-7.3€
Spain	+14.22€	+9.62€	-3.41€	+12.03€	+13.95€	-13.32€	+26.74€	-13.42€
Germany	+17.61€	+6.38€	+2.55€	+15.68€	+18.03€	-20.22€	+32.05e	-11.83€
Portugal	+15.72€	+30.54€	-19.07€	+7.65€	+6.34€	-13.23€	+21.98€	-8.75€
Switzerland	+3.50€	+0.62€	+5.63€	-4.52€	+6.37€	-4.63€	+9.08€	-4.45€
Generation Z	+2.73€	+13.29€	+2.46€	+12.35€	+13.18€	-19.24€	+21.32€	-2.08€
Millennials	+4.67€	+3.3€	+1.98€	-2.52€	+11.72€	-9.54€	+18.11€	-8.57€
Generation X	+9.59€	+10.92€	-4.41€	+5.19€	+6.32€	-8.14€	+14.87€	-6.73€
Boomers	+3.83€	+7.97€	-0.66€	+5.72€	+7.06€	-5.93€	+10.27€	-4.34€
Diploma	+5.47€	+10.5€	-0.38€	+5.42€	+10.52€	-9.62€	+14.72€	-5.10€
Bachelor	+5.93€	+8.37€	-2.34€	+1.65€	+6.25€	-10.03€	+15.71€	-5.68€
Master	+5.48€	-0.41€	+4.40€	+2.27€	+5.80€	-6.57€	+13.16€	18.16€
PhD	+9.38€	+6.86€	-3.24€	+10.72€	+5.27€	-6.13€	+18.16€	-12.03€
Male	+7.56€	+5.97€	-0.81€	+4.59€	+10.36€	-9.20€	+17.84€	-8.01€
Female	+3.41€	+10.33€	-0.32€	+3.68€	+7.59€	-9.20€	+13.02€	-3.82€
< 20.000€	+5.66€	+11.37€	-3.40€	+7.74€	+6.42€	-11.27€	+17.08€	-5.81€
20.000€ - 40.000€	+1.18€	+14.39€	-3.76€	+5.21€	+10.59€	-10.35€	+15.85€	-5.50€
40.000€ - 60.000€	+7.98€	+4.99€	+1.96€	+1.98€	+10.76€	-9.15€	+14.57€	-5.42€
60.000€ - 80.000€	+11.80€	+2.87€	+3.37€	+7.46€	+11.87€	-11.28€	+21.8€	-10.52€
> 80.000€	+7.16€	-1.02€	+4.43€	-1.68€	+4.77€	-4.74€	+9.79€	-5.05€

Hyaluronic Acid-Based Cosmetics

The analysis of the WTP values for the cosmetic product reveals a clear preference among consumers for sustainability-oriented and performance-enhancing features, particularly those related to packaging solutions, ingredient types, and emission reductions. Attributes perceived as aligning with environmental responsibility or product innovation tend to receive higher monetary valuations, while conventional or less differentiated features often generate negative WTP.

Across the total sample, the most highly valued attribute was refillable packaging, with a WTP of €+10.57, followed closely by carbon-neutral production (€+15.9) and biodegradable ingredients (€+10.86). These figures indicate that consumers strongly associate sustainability with value and are willing to pay a premium for features that reflect concrete, recognizable ecological benefits. Conversely, standard formulations across multiple categories—such as standard packaging (€-26.04), standard product effect (€-14.99), and standard emissions (€-12.64)—were assigned negative WTP, highlighting widespread aversion to non-innovative or non-sustainable options.

In terms of packaging preferences, refillable solutions were valued most positively, followed by bio-based materials (€+8.34) and recycled packaging (€+7.13). The particularly strong WTP for refillable packaging likely reflects its perceived role in reducing long-term waste and offering a practical, environmentally friendly option. The strong negative valuation for standard packaging suggests that consumers not only prefer eco-friendly alternatives but actively reject traditional plastic formats, viewing them as outdated or inconsistent with sustainability expectations. These figures are consistent with prior findings from the detergent and textile case studies, where packaging consistently emerged as one of the most appreciated sustainability features. This widespread preference for sustainable packaging can be attributed to the fact that it offers consumers a visible and immediately comprehensible indicator of reduced environmental impact. Unlike more abstract sustainability features—such as carbon emissions or ingredient sourcing—packaging represents a tangible, physical change that is easy to recognize and evaluate at the point of purchase. Consumers often associate sustainable packaging with responsible brand behavior and find it easier to connect this attribute with a lower ecological footprint, reinforcing its relevance in both practical and symbolic dimensions. Despite the differences in material types, the high WTP values across all three sustainable packaging formats (refillable, recycled, and bio-based) indicate that packaging is not only central to perceived product sustainability, but also serves as a key differentiator in the market. This trend highlights the importance for manufacturers and marketers to emphasize packaging innovations in their product development and communication strategies, as they offer an effective and credible lever to engage sustainability-oriented consumers.

Within the emissions category, the carbon-neutral option recorded the highest willingness to pay (WTP) at €+15.9, while the option for a 25% reduction in carbon emissions surprisingly received a negative WTP of €-3.26. This result is somewhat unexpected, as it would be more logical to see a positive, though smaller, WTP for partial emission reductions—especially given growing public awareness of environmental issues. However, this result can be explained by how consumers perceive and compare different sustainability claims. When carbon neutrality is presented alongside a partial reduction, the more ambitious option may set a strong benchmark in consumers' minds. In comparison, the 25% reduction might seem like too small of an effort, or not enough to really make a difference. Some consumers may even question whether such claims are truly meaningful or just a marketing strategy with little impact. The strong WTP for carbon-neutral products likely comes from the fact that these claims are easier to understand and feel more complete—like the company has taken full responsibility for its environmental footprint. A partial reduction, instead, may seem vague or less trustworthy, especially when it's directly compared to a "100% carbon-neutral" alternative. If it might seem strange at first, this difference in WTP shows that consumers are more attracted to clear and bold sustainability goals, and may overlook or undervalue more moderate improvements if

they're not explained clearly. For companies, this highlights the need to communicate the value of incremental changes more effectively, especially when they can't yet reach full neutrality.

Regarding product effect, the highest value was assigned to anti-aging properties (€+6.88), followed by deep hydration (€+5.16). Meanwhile, standard effects were devalued (WTP: €-14.99), signaling the importance of perceived innovation and efficacy in personal care. These findings emphasize that consumers expect more than basic functionality from cosmetic products and associate specialized effects with enhanced product worth. This trend aligns closely with findings from the detergent case study, where—although sustainability attributes received the highest WTP—product effectiveness remained a key factor in purchase decisions. In both product categories, it is evident that consumers prioritize environmental responsibility, but they are not willing to sacrifice performance. This reinforces the idea that sustainability must go hand in hand with efficacy to be truly competitive in the consumer market.

The analysis of ingredient preferences revealed nuanced consumer attitudes. Biodegradable ingredients achieved a high WTP of €+10.86, suggesting that end-of-life product impact is a tangible concern for consumers. Bio-based ingredients also received a positive WTP (€+6.82), whereas vegan formulations were associated with a strong negative WTP (€-10.82). This result is particularly striking and suggests that vegan claims, while ethically significant for some, may not carry universal appeal—potentially due to skepticism, limited understanding, or perceived compromises in efficacy. It is also possible that vegan claims are associated more with lifestyle branding than with tangible product benefits, making them less persuasive in contexts where function and science-driven performance are prioritized. Another important factor to consider is the actual proportion of vegan individuals within the sample. If the share of vegan respondents is low, it is reasonable to expect that the majority of participants may not find this attribute personally relevant, which would naturally result in a lower or even negative average WTP. This suggests that while the vegan label may be meaningful to a specific niche, its appeal in the broader market remains limited—particularly in product categories where performance, results, and safety are dominant purchase drivers.

These findings highlight the difference between what consumers say matters to them and what they are actually willing to pay for. There is a notable consistency where packaging—identified in the survey as the most important attribute—also receives a high WTP (€+10.57), suggesting strong alignment between stated and revealed preferences. Similarly, product efficacy, often considered a baseline expectation, is rated as less important and receives a lower yet still positive WTP (€+6.66), reflecting its perceived necessity rather than added value. However, the high WTP for the carbon neutral claim (€+15.90), despite fewer consumers selecting it as a top priority in the survey, reveals a disconnect between direct responses and actual choice behavior. This likely reflects cognitive bias—consumers may not consciously rank carbon neutrality as a key factor, but when faced with a purchasing scenario, they assign it high value, possibly due to its strong symbolic link to climate action. As seen in similar product categories like detergents, this gap between stated and revealed preferences is common and underscores the importance of analyzing both types of data to understand what truly drives purchasing decisions.

Demographic segmentation provides further insight. Women consistently showed higher WTP than men for sustainability-focused features, particularly refillable packaging (€+13.27) and biodegradable ingredients (€+6.6). Men, by contrast, expressed slightly higher WTP for carbon neutrality (€+17.68) and refillable packaging (€+14.37), possibly reflecting a technical appreciation of climate-friendly features. Interestingly, female respondents assigned more negative values to standard features (e.g., €-22.48 for standard product effect), suggesting greater selectivity or higher expectations in cosmetic performance. As expected, female respondents also demonstrated significantly higher WTP for performance-related attributes, with €+12.00 for deep hydration and €+10.48 for anti-aging hydration. These values suggest a strong focus on functional results, likely due to higher familiarity with the product category and greater involvement in daily skincare routines. The slightly lower WTP for the anti-aging effect may be explained by its perceived association with

a higher product cost or by the idea that hydration is a universally desired benefit, while anti-aging is more relevant to a specific consumer segment. In contrast, male respondents reported substantially lower WTP for these same attributes, with only €+3.73 for deep hydration and €+2.94 for anti-aging hydration. While these figures still indicate a positive perception of performance, they highlight a less pronounced emphasis on product efficacy among men, which could stem from lower product familiarity or less demanding expectations. Overall, these differences underline the need for gender-sensitive positioning strategies in the cosmetics market, particularly when highlighting product effectiveness.

Generational analysis shows that Generation Z respondents were especially responsive to sustainability aspects, reporting high WTP for features like biodegradable ingredients (€+10.12) and refillable packaging (€+12.32). Millennials exhibited similar patterns, while Generation X and Boomers showed more balanced preferences, valuing practicality and efficacy (e.g., Gen X: €+10.88 for anti-aging effect; Boomers: €+15.24 for deep hydration). The younger cohorts' pronounced preference for ecological attributes may reflect both value alignment and increased exposure to environmental messaging. These findings are consistent with what is generally expected from age-based segmentation, where younger consumers are typically more attentive to environmental issues and tend to prioritize sustainability attributes. Their higher WTP for green features may reflect both a stronger value alignment with ecological concerns and a higher exposure to sustainability messaging in education, media, and brand communication. Meanwhile, older generations appear more focused on proven product benefits and performance, which are likely more aligned with their daily priorities and usage expectations.

In terms of income, consumers earning between €60,000 and €80,000 displayed the highest WTP for multiple attributes, particularly biodegradable ingredients (€+8.47) and carbon-neutral cosmetics (€+15.31). Notably, the lowest WTP across most categories was reported among those earning less than €20,000, reinforcing the barrier that affordability poses to sustainable product adoption. Consumers in this group assigned negative WTP even to partially improved features such as a 25% emission reduction (€-1.16) indicating both constrained willingness and possibly skepticism toward mid-tier environmental claims.

Educational background also influenced WTP, often in unexpected ways. Respondents with Ph.D.s showed polarized results, with very high premiums for carbon neutrality (€+32.49) and biodegradable ingredients (€+52.75), but strong rejection of standard and vegan formulations (€-9.55 for vegan ingredients). This group may be more analytically engaged, favoring comprehensive environmental benefits but skeptical of marketing terms perceived as vague or unsubstantiated. Participants with bachelor's degrees showed more balanced preferences, while those with only high school education also reported high WTP for recycled and biodegradable packaging, indicating that sustainability features are widely valued across education levels, albeit for potentially different reasons.

Cross-country comparisons revealed significant cultural and market-specific differences. Spanish consumers assigned the highest WTP values across nearly all attributes, including €+42.13 for carbon neutrality, €+22.69 for anti-aging effect, and €+36.04 for biodegradable ingredients. This may reflect strong public engagement with sustainability, combined with effective communication from local brands. Conversely, Portuguese and German respondents displayed more cautious preferences, with more modest premiums for sustainable packaging and ingredients and stronger negative WTP for standard offerings. Italian consumers showed strong preferences for refillable packaging (€+18.13) and bio-based ingredients (€+25.78), but penalized standard emission levels (€-21.55), reinforcing their attention to climate-impacting features. Swiss respondents demonstrated more nuanced behavior, with some of the most extreme values across the sample: highly negative WTP for vegan ingredients (€-23.59) and standard packaging (€-33.61), but high WTP for biodegradable ingredients (€+16.53), reflecting polarized consumer segments or distinct market dynamics. What is particularly noteworthy is that the results observed for Spain (strong sustainability preference) and for Germany and Portugal (more reserved toward green attributes) are perfectly consistent

with the findings from the detergent study, despite the completely different sampling methods used in the two surveys. This alignment strengthens the validity of the outcomes and demonstrates that the sample is robust, and the trends identified are reliable. Such consistency across independent datasets suggests that national-level consumer orientations toward sustainability are both stable and meaningful, offering valuable insight for market strategies and policy design. The variation in consumer preferences observed across different countries can be explained by a combination of cultural values, policy environments, market maturity, and economic conditions. Countries such as Spain show very high willingness to pay (WTP) for sustainability-related attributes, which may be linked to several factors: a strong national discourse on environmental issues, the presence of active public policies promoting green consumption, and widespread consumer education around sustainability. Additionally, Spanish brands and retailers may have effectively integrated environmental messaging into their marketing strategies, increasing consumer awareness and receptivity. In contrast, countries like Portugal and Germany, which showed more cautious attitudes, may reflect a different cultural or market context. However, it is important to emphasize that accurately understanding why these geographical differences emerge is highly complex. It would require an in-depth analysis that considers multiple interconnected dimensions, including national policy frameworks, education systems, media influence, and marketing practices. The explanations offered here are theoretical hypotheses based on contextual interpretation and should not be considered conclusive. At present, there is no direct evidence within this dataset that confirms the underlying causes of such differences, and any attempt to generalize must be made with caution. Overall, these geographic variations highlight how local context can deeply influence consumer behavior toward sustainable products. For companies and policymakers, this reinforces the need to tailor sustainability strategies to national realities, rather than assuming a uniform response across all markets.

In summary, the cosmetic Choice Experiment confirms that consumers strongly favor products that are clearly aligned with sustainability goals, especially those offering refillable packaging, carbon-neutral production, and biodegradable or bio-based ingredients. However, the acceptance of these features varies across demographic segments, and negative WTP for certain claims—such as vegan formulations—highlights the importance of clear, credible, and value-linked messaging. Financial capacity remains a key determinant of sustainable purchasing, while gender, age, and education modulate preferences based on perceived efficacy, ethical alignment, or brand trust. These findings emphasize the need for tailored marketing, pricing strategies, and transparent sustainability communication in promoting the adoption of eco-conscious cosmetics across diverse consumer groups.

However, it is important to consider that cosmetics are not 'neutral' products, and consumers' WTP in this category (**Table 6**) is often influenced by emotional, sensory, and personal factors. This means that choice behavior may reflect deeper values or perceptions beyond the functional attributes presented, such as trust in the brand, perceived self-image, or product experience. As a result, WTP outcomes in cosmetics should be interpreted with care, acknowledging that they may not solely reflect the objective value of sustainability features, but also the unique role these products play in consumers' daily lives.

Table 6. Willingness to pay (WTP) for each attribute according to socioeconomic and demographic information. For the country-specific analysis, only the countries in which the partners are based are shown. -25E = -25% emissions; CN = carbon neutral; RP = recyclable packaging; BBP = bio-based packaging; RFP = refillable packaging; DH = Deep hydration; AA = anti-age; VI= vegan ingredients; BBI = bio-based ingredients; BI = biodegradable ingredients.

Sample	-25E	CN	RP	BP	RFP	DH	AA	VI	BBI	BI
		+15.90			+10.57					
Total	-3.26 €	€	+7.13 €	+8.34 €	€	+8.11 €	+6.88 €	-10.82 €	+6.82 €	+10.86 €
		+11.79	+13.83	+18.13	+14.43					
Italy	-0.44 €	+8.47 €	€	€	€	€	+12.71 €	+8.28 €	+3.06 €	+3.39 €
		+42.13								
Spain	-34.66 €	€	-3.45 €	+3.15 €	+3.30 €	+2.89 €	-25.58 €	-51.70 €	+8.31 €	+36.04 €

Portugal	-0.46 €	+15.27 €	+7.31 €	+7.93 €	+10.43 €	+5.66 €	+7.19 €	-3.97 €	+4.06 €	+9.33 €
Germany	-15.93 €	+30.00 €	+3.59 €	+6.23 €	+1.26 €	+3.49 €	-4.04 €	-9.55 €	+0.30 €	+17.21 €
Switzerland	-3.86 €	+22.35 €	+8.85 €	+11.17 €	+13.59 €	+7.92 €	+12.01 €	-23.59 €	+11.17 €	+16.53 €
Generation Z	-2.51 €	+16.21 €	+7.99 €	+6.64 €	+12.30 €	+5.74 €	+5.44 €	-10.77 €	+8.26 €	+10.12 €
Millennials	-0.51 €	+15.19 €	+6.64 €	+9.87 €	+5.99 €	+13.58 €	+10.88 €	-13.16 €	+12.25 €	+10.27 €
Generation X	-8.39 €	+19.17 €	+6.56 €	+8.13 €	+11.80 €	+10.16 €	+2.05 €	-8.22 €	+2.87 €	+13.04 €
Boomers	-1.16 €	+12.91 €	+7.21 €	+9.34 €	+11.07 €	+5.24 €	+9.05 €	-12.96 €	+6.56 €	+10.26 €
Diploma	-2.92 €	+14.93 €	+12.05 €	+8.55 €	+18.86 €	+3.36 €	+7.62 €	-21.13 €	+12.54 €	+13.64 €
Bachelor	-0.67 €	+15.89 €	+7.30 €	+9.22 €	+14.98 €	+12.39 €	+10.76 €	-18.73 €	+10.15 €	+14.61 €
Master	-6.86 €	+19.88 €	+7.24 €	+11.86 €	+4.10 €	+6.95 €	+4.74 €	-12.59 €	+9.74 €	+10.07 €
PhD	32.49 €	-6.80 €	+11.14 €	+14.85 €	-8.18 €	7.31 €	-1.05 €	+67.71 €	+29.64 €	-52.75 €
Male	-5.43 €	+17.68 €	+7.31 €	+7.52 €	+14.37 €	+3.73 €	+2.94 €	-23.14 €	+10.09 €	+15.51 €
Female	-1.47 €	+14.32 €	+6.99 €	+9.05 €	+7.11 €	+12.00 €	+10.48 €	-0.88 €	+5.09 €	+6.60 €
<20,000€	-6.61 €	+20.25 €	+9.74 €	+7.53 €	+9.32 €	+2.05 €	+2.85 €	-17.66 €	+8.70 €	+14.65 €
20,000€-40,000€	-4.32 €	+15.74 €	+4.84 €	+6.51 €	+9.93 €	+7.58 €	+6.43 €	-8.63 €	+4.87 €	+9.98 €
40,000€ - 60,000€	-1.63 €	+15.31 €	+6.83 €	+8.32 €	+12.15 €	+10.69 €	+9.30 €	-4.81 €	+3.56 €	+9.48 €
60,000€ - 80,000€	2.63 €	+11.29 €	+11.75 €	+18.05 €	+16.58 €	+16.01 €	-17.84 €	+19.16 €	+8.47 €	
> 80,000€	6.03 €	+7.72 €	+15.52 €	+13.04 €	+25.78 €	+10.21 €	+12.26 €	+23.31 €	+11.72 €	

5.2.4 Limits of the study

Although the CE methodology has been validated in different studies, contextual limitations of this analysis should be considered when interpreting its findings:

- **Omission of sensory and brand-related attributes:** Attributes such as fragrance, texture, brand, or packaging design — commonly influential in real-life choices — were excluded. Their absence may have biased respondents toward evaluating sustainability features more heavily than they would under real market conditions.
- **Focus on selected consumer products:** This study is limited to consumer products targeted by the FuturEnzyme project—namely, detergents, textiles, and cosmetics. These products can vary widely in composition and functional characteristics compared to other items found in supermarkets. As a result, the measured attributes and resulting real-life choices may not be directly comparable to other product types or broader market segments.
- **Use of hypothetical scenarios:** The Choice Experiment methodology, while powerful, is inherently based on hypothetical scenarios. This introduces the risk of hypothetical bias—where participants stated preferences or willingness to pay do not fully align with actual purchasing behaviour. Although the design included a no-choice option to simulate realism as well as labels and images to encourage

product visualisation, respondents were not under financial or experiential constraints typical of real transactions.

- **Limited geographic representativeness:** while the textile and cosmetic surveys were conducted through controlled panels with demographic balancing, the detergent survey relied on public distribution, resulting in an unbalanced sample. Countries outside the project's partner network were underrepresented, limiting cross-European generalizability. Despite this limitation, however, the detergent study provided a concrete example of a fully open-access study.
- **Underrepresentation of Specific Subgroups:** certain segments, such as individuals with annual incomes above €80,000 or those with Ph.D.s, were underrepresented. In cases where these groups were included, the small sample size reduced the statistical robustness of findings, and in some cases (specifically for the detergent) led to anomalous or inconsistent WTP values. However, this reflects the low representativeness of these categories in a real-world scenario.
- **Potential misinterpretation of technical attributes:** Attributes such as “carbon neutral,” “reduction in microplastics,” or “renewable surfactants” may not have been fully understood by all respondents. Although visual aids and simplified language were used, the interpretation of these features may vary across educational and cultural backgrounds, potentially affecting response consistency.
- **Absence of longitudinal or behavioural validation:** The study captures preferences at a single point in time. It does not verify whether these preferences translate into repeat behaviour or long-term purchasing habits. Further longitudinal or experimental validation could enhance the reliability of findings.
- **Limits of the open access approach:** The use of Google Form and R for these studies, despite being an added value as it provides concrete examples on how to implement these studies with open access software, presents intrinsic constraints. On the survey side, it limits the ability to control sample composition and enforce demographic quotas, as evidenced in the detergent case. For this reason, the textile and cosmetic surveys transitioned to Qualtrics to ensure greater control and sample homogeneity. On the analysis side, while R provides flexibility and open access capabilities, its computational performance can be limiting when processing complex CE designs or large data sets.

These limitations offer valuable directions for future studies, suggesting the integration of behavioural testing, enhanced demographic balancing, and more immersive or real-time decision simulations to validate choice-based findings.

6. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that sustainability is no longer a peripheral concern for consumers—it is central to **purchasing decisions** across diverse product categories. While product performance remains a relevant consideration, European consumers show a consistent and measurable willingness to pay for environmentally friendly product features. However, the findings also reveal that not all sustainability claims are equally understood or valued, and **demographic factors significantly influence consumer preferences**. Consistently across the three studies, younger consumers emerged as enthusiastic about green features, while higher-income consumers exhibited the highest WTP due to greater financial capacity. Additionally, national and cultural contexts shaped sustainability perceptions, underlining the importance of designing differentiated strategies for product development, marketing, and communication.

Therefore, these results reinforce the importance of **transparent, clear, and credible sustainability communication**. To foster adoption, companies must ensure that sustainable attributes are not only technically robust but also emotionally resonant and easy to interpret. Policymakers, in turn, should support education and standardization initiatives to reduce confusion around eco-claims and help bridge the gap between awareness and action.

Beyond its immediate application in product development, the structured workflow applied here demonstrates how consumer-cantered experimental designs can be used also to **inform the direction of**

future research and innovation. By identifying which sustainability features are truly valued by consumers—and which are not—such tools can help prioritize R&D investments and align product innovations with real market expectations.

In this sense, studies like this are not only useful for market analysis but are also critical instruments for shaping the next generation of sustainable, enzyme-enabled consumer products. They bridge the gap between technological feasibility and social desirability, ensuring that future innovations are both impactful and accepted.

6.1 Recommendations

Based on the insights generated through this study, several strategic directions can be identified to support the development and market integration of enzyme-enabled sustainable products. These recommendations are particularly relevant for companies operating in the detergent, textile, and cosmetic sectors:

1. **Prioritize packaging innovation in product design:** Consumers consistently placed high value on packaging features such as recyclability, refillability, and plastic reduction, especially for cosmetics and detergents. Companies are encouraged to invest in eco-design strategies that minimize packaging material—e.g., adopting refill systems, biobased containers, or plastic-free alternatives. These features are not only environmentally beneficial but are also strongly perceived as credible sustainability signals by consumers.
2. **Advance sustainable formulations with clear added value:** Attributes such as the use of biodegradable, bio-based, or renewable ingredients—especially in detergents and cosmetics—were widely appreciated and associated with high willingness to pay. Industry actors should accelerate the integration of these innovations and clearly differentiate them in marketing materials, emphasizing their environmental contribution without relying on vague or generic claims.
3. **Balance environmental innovation with product performance:** Across all product categories, performance-related features—such as stain removal, hydration, or textile quality—remained important, though often secondary to sustainability. It is essential that new formulations and materials maintain high functional standards and that this is clearly communicated to consumers. Demonstrating that green products do not compromise on efficacy will be key to achieving widespread market acceptance.
4. **Segment and tailor offerings to diverse consumer profiles:** The study revealed meaningful differences in sustainability preferences across demographic groups, including age, gender, education, and income. Companies should consider these variations when developing product lines and communication strategies. For example, younger consumers may prioritize recyclability and innovation, while older groups may respond more strongly to credible performance claims paired with sustainability.
5. **Leverage consumer data to guide product and R&D strategy:** The Choice Experiment approach used in this study offers a robust, evidence-based framework for identifying which features consumers truly value. By grounding R&D and product development decisions in empirical data on consumer preferences, companies can align innovation efforts with market demand—enhancing both the environmental and economic viability of new enzyme-based solutions.

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